

Roadmaps, White Paper and Value Added Reports v4

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Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive and consolidated overview of outcomes, future trends, lessons learned, and best practices from past and current security research projects focused on the protection and resilience of Europe's Critical Infrastructures (CI) and Critical Entities (CE). Special attention is given to the technological, industrial, legal, and ethical dimensions that shape the evolving landscape of CIP/CIR.

As the latest instalment in the EU-CIP series of Roadmaps, White Papers, and Value-Added Reports, this edition builds on previous analyses by aggregating new insights from stakeholder surveys and expert consultations. These efforts illuminate current gaps, emerging needs, and stakeholder-driven visions for advancing CIP and CIR from multiple perspectives.

Key highlights of this report include:

- **Stakeholder-Based Insights:** Drawing on extensive surveys, the report presents visions and recommendations from across the stakeholder community, addressing how technological, industrial, legal, and ethical factors can drive improvement in CIP and CIR.
- **Market and Sector Trends:** The analysis incorporates recent market trends and identifies technologies and strategies that can address existing gaps. The report also features sector-specific insights, with links to in-depth white papers covering areas such as energy, finance, space, telecommunications, transport, and water.
- **Best Practices and Lessons Learned:** By consolidating lessons learned and best practices from a wide range of security research projects, the report provides actionable guidance for stakeholders aiming to enhance the resilience and security of critical infrastructures.

This report is part of a regularly updated series, produced every six months, that supports the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub and informs the next phase of the project. Each edition builds on the last, refining the roadmap, updating capability needs, and deepening sectoral insights to provide stakeholders with the latest intelligence and strategic foresight.

By continuously updating and sharing these findings, the EU-CIP project empowers policymakers, industry leaders, and practitioners with the knowledge and tools needed to address emerging threats, close capability gaps, and build a more secure and resilient critical infrastructure ecosystem for Europe.

White papers referenced in this report are available through the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub: <https://knowledgehub.eucip.eu/>.

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Definitions and acronyms

3D	3 dimensional
4G	fourth generation of cellular network technology
5G	fifth generation of cellular network technology
AFAS	Advanced File Analysis System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AML	Anti-Money Laundering
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BCG	Business Continuity Game
BI	Business Intelligence
BMS	Building Management System
BTDS	BMS Threat Detection System
BTMS	Building Threat Monitoring System
CDB	Central DataBase
CE	Critical Entity
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CER	Critical Entities Resilience
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
CIR	Critical Infrastructure Resilience
CL3	Cluster 3
COVID	COroNaVirus Disease
COVID19	COroNaVirus Disease 2019
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CROP	Common Relevant Operational Picture
CSA	Cyber Security Awareness
CTMS	Cyber Threat Monitoring System
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
DCS	Data Collection System
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
DRCN	Design of Reliable Communication Networks
DS	Decision Support
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Decision Support System
DXL	Data Exchange Layer
EC	European Commission
ECCC	European Cybersecurity Competence Centre
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECI	European Critical Infrastructure
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
ECSS	European Cooperation for Space Standardization
EDSA	E-health Devices Security Analytics

EO	Earth Observation
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FD	Final Demo
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GSaaS	Ground Station-as-a-Service
HAMS	Hospital Availability Management System
HSA	Hybrid Situational Awareness
HSOC	Holistic Security Operation Centre
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IFDS	Intrusion and Fire Detection System
IOT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPDSM	Impact Propagation and Decision Support Model
IRG	Technische Hochschule Köln, Institut für Rettungswesen und Gefahrenabwehr
ISAC	Information Sharing and Analysis Centre
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
ITTDS	IT threat detection system
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
MAS	Mobile Alerting System
ML	Machine Learning
NCC	National Coordination Centre
NIS, NIS2	Directive on security of network and information systems
OC	Open Call
OODA	Observe, Orient, Decide, and Act
OT	Operational Technology
PSA	Physical Security Awareness
PSIM	Physical Security Information Management
PU	Public
SBDS	Suspicious Behaviour Detection System
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SCI	Smart Critical Infrastructure
SEN	Sensitive
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SOC	Security Operations Centre
SPoC	Single Point of Contact

SSRI	Strengthened Security Research and Innovation
TC	Technical Committee
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TOC	Table of Content
TRAS	Threat Response and Alert System
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UAV	Unmanned/Uninhabited/Unpiloted Aerial Vehicle
US	United States
USA	United States of America
USD	US Dollar
ZTA	Zero Trust Architecture

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Roadmap

The EU-CIP roadmap series is designed to advance Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) across Europe. In an era marked by increasing interconnectedness and evolving threats, safeguarding critical infrastructure is essential for ensuring the stability, security, and prosperity of our societies. Earlier editions of this series introduced the foundational concepts and provided a consolidated view of capability needs and gaps in CIP and CIR.

The roadmap sets out a new vision for intelligent, automated, predictive, and collaborative protection of critical infrastructures. This approach addresses recent challenges in the CIP/CIR landscape, including the rise of asymmetric, hybrid, and cyber-physical attacks, as well as new vulnerabilities emerging from shifting geopolitical and technological environments. Recent events, such as the widespread impact of the CrowdStrike Falcon platform outage, highlight how deeply integrated security solutions can themselves become sources of risk—underscoring the need for a holistic and adaptive approach. Accordingly, the roadmap not only recommends a range of targeted measures and activities but also emphasizes their integration into a cohesive strategy for enhanced resilience.

This edition highlights technological outcomes, breakthrough innovations, and key advancements introduced by recent security research projects. It also explores industry-driven transformations and trends, addresses prevailing technological challenges, and examines the latest legal and ethical developments. By drawing on stakeholder experiences and expectations, the roadmap helps shape frameworks for ethical decision-making and guides future developments.

Overall, this roadmap provides actionable ideas to:

- Enhance security,
- Foster collaboration,
- Ensure compliance with regulations and standards,
- Accelerate innovation, and
- Enable the strategic allocation of resources.

Through these efforts, the EU-CIP roadmap series supports the creation of a secure, resilient, and adaptive critical infrastructure ecosystem, capable of meeting the complex challenges of today and tomorrow.

Note that several of the resources and content referenced in the scope of the document are available through the project's knowledge hub at: <https://knowledgehub.eucip.eu/>.

1.2. Scope and Objectives

This roadmap provides an aggregated and consolidated view of outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt, and best practices derived from past and current security research projects that can help close the identified capability gaps in CIP/CIR and aims to address the multi-layered challenges associated with improving the protection and resilience of critical infrastructure. It covers different sectors such as energy, transport, communications, water supply and healthcare and considers their interdependencies and the cascading effects of disruptions.

To achieve an adequate oversight and foster the foresight, EU-CIP settles a methodological framework which considers the needed data base and spans the evaluation of technologies from state-of-the-art over emerging ones and includes surveys on supporting R&I activities.

1.3. Relationship to Previous Roadmaps

To provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR), the EU-CIP project has been tasked with delivering a series of six roadmap documents. Each document contributes unique insights and guidance toward enhancing the protection and resilience of critical infrastructures.

The first document in the series, v1, laid the foundation by introducing the project's scope and identifying an initial set of capability needs and gaps. The second document, v2, built upon this by offering an aggregated and consolidated view of these needs and gaps, along with preliminary elements of strategies to address them.

The third document provided initial insights into research and technological developments aimed at closing the identified gaps. The current document expands on this by offering a more detailed examination of research, technological, and industrial developments, while also exploring the legal, ethical, and standards landscape relevant to CIP/CIR.

This comprehensive approach aims to identify areas requiring improvement and to guide society in strategically strengthening legal and ethical frameworks to support current and future CIP/CIR challenges.

2. Methodological Framework

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

To develop a comprehensive roadmap for Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience, a multifaceted methodology is employed that combines literature reviews, stakeholder engagement, data collection, analysis, and visualization to ensure comprehensive coverage of all identified research items.

The process began with a thorough review of existing literature on critical infrastructure protection and resilience, encompassing academic studies, industry reports, and government guidelines. Additionally, relevant stakeholders were approached by dedicated surveys and during online workshops as well as onsite conferences to gather their expert's knowledge about the different facets of CIP/CIR. This provided a solid foundation for understanding the current state of knowledge in the field and identifying areas for further research.

Stakeholder engagement is crucial to gather perspectives and insights from policy makers, practitioners and experts in all critical infrastructure sectors considered in this document. This involved conducting interviews, surveys, and focus groups to capture diverse viewpoints and experiences.

2.1. Data Collection process

The specific topics of the current roadmap document required the invention of customised surveys to obtain the desired input. The data collection relied on a variety of sources, including national and international surveys, industry reports, government databases, social media platforms and online forums. In addition, the in-depth expertise of the EU-CIP project partners also provided a rich basis for specific questions on the topics.

Therefore, EU-CIP provided three dedicated surveys aimed to receive latest stakeholder knowledge about

- i) Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience: outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt and best practices from past and current security research projects.
- ii) The EU CER Directive on the resilience of critical entities.
- iii) EU legal, ethical and standardisation frameworks.

The "data" in the tasks above are primarily information and opinions and not the data in the sense of "big data". Hence, not or only to a very limited extent suitable for quantitative analysis.

2.2. Analysis Techniques

A web-semantics based tool for analysis of the above information ("data") is provided in the FAIR Observatory. And it can be applied to any text entries in the Observatory: standards, research outcomes, survey results, taxonomies, indicators, etc. The tool has so far been used only for providing examples, in a particular case on the standards and to identify the relationships which may be identified among the information items (e.g., text descriptions of single standards).

Based on the results of the semantic analysis the relationships can be graphically depicted as a network (Figure 1). This is of a practical advantage for the user as she/he can gain an overview of the related information. For example, as shown in figure below, the result includes the links among the relevant standards retrieved through the search for terms "guidelines" & "risk".

Figure 1: Analysing relationships among standards corresponding to the search on "risk" & "guidelines"

In general, the transition for "hard" (conventional) analysis tools towards the "soft" ones, based on the wide-spread use of smart/AI techniques is the way to go in the area of the analysis techniques.

3. Research and technological development

Survey overview and participants

The survey named "Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience: outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt and best practices from past and current security research projects" was prepared by SINTEF, ENG, DLR and distributed to the EU-CIP coordinators of CIP and CIR projects. Link to the survey: [EU-CIP FAIR Data Observatory > Survey.](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

The survey engaged 21 coordinators from security research projects listed in the [ECSCI](#) cluster, achieving an exceptionally high response rate, with over 89% of participants answering most of the questions. This strong level of engagement reflects the relevance and importance of the topics covered.

Participants represented a geographically diverse group, with 33.33% based in Spain. Other European countries, including Greece, Germany, Ireland, Italy and Norway, were represented in roughly equal numbers at 9.5% each. Additionally, 19.05% of respondents were from other, unspecified locations, broadening the survey's geographic outreach.

Respondents came from various organization types, with the majority (again: 33.33%) representing the industry sector. Research institutions followed at 19.05%, while universities, IT&C companies, and private-sector entities accounted for smaller proportions. However, detailed demographic information, such as job titles or years of experience, was not available in the data set.

The survey was conducted online, ensuring efficient data collection and processing, which was managed by Steinbeis sEU-VRi utilising the functionalities of the FAIR observatory. This approach facilitated robust data capture, providing valuable insights into the survey's objectives while achieving broad participation.

The contributing projects covered various critical infrastructure sectors, with energy, transport, healthcare, and telecommunications being frequently mentioned. Many projects also addressed several sectors simultaneously and analysed connected critical infrastructures, such as e.g. transport AND energy AND healthcare or other combinations. Projects' durations ranged between 2 and 4 years, showcasing a variety of timelines for tackling complex challenges. This breadth underscores the dynamic and multifaceted nature of security research across critical infrastructures.

“Figure 2” provides an overview of EU projects related to CIR/CIP, as identified by Open Call A winners. The list serves as a valuable resource, mapping projects that have not yet been covered by the survey and will be addressed in the development of the remaining roadmaps.

Figure 2: Distribution of survey participants amongst EU member states (Survey: Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience: outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt and best practices from past and current security research projects).

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
Blue	Industry	7	33.33 %	Yellow	Research Institution	4	19.05 %	Red	No answer	2	9.52 %	Dark Blue	Other	8	38.10 %

Figure 3: Distribution of survey participants on organisation type (Survey: Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience: outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt and best practices from past and current security research projects).

3.1. Technological outcomes, breakthrough technologies and innovations introduced by projects

The survey highlighted a diverse array of technological outcomes developed by the participating projects. A common theme was the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) for enhancing risk assessment, threat detection, and incident response through specific applications ranging from identifying vulnerabilities and simulating attacks to detecting anomalies and mitigating risks. **Digital twin** technology also emerged as a frequently used approach, enabling the simulation of scenarios such as cyberattacks and physical disruptions, thereby improving (stress)testing and preparedness.

While many responses emphasized the use of AI, details about specific algorithms or implementations were often lacking. Similarly, although the digital twin approach was frequently mentioned, precise descriptions of its application are limited. Nevertheless, the need for the consistent use of AI/ML for risk assessment, threat detection and prediction are obvious.

Additionally, **advanced risk assessment** methodologies were employed, ranging from traditional static approaches to dynamic, real-time assessments tailored to specific sectors.

Some projects utilized **blockchain** technology to secure data and enhance operational transparency. Projects also developed various tools to support situational awareness and incident response, and to enhance cybersecurity systems. Key solutions include risk assessment tools, intrusion detection systems, simulation platforms, and data analytics systems. These tools underscore the breadth and sophistication of the technological innovations pursued by the projects.

To conclude, common themes include:

- **Advanced risk assessment methodologies:** Various approaches were used to assess risks, from traditional static methods to dynamic, real-time assessments tailored to specific sectors.

- **AI/ML for threat detection and response:** Many projects integrated AI and ML for enhanced risk assessment, threat detection, and incident response. Specific applications included vulnerability identification, attack simulation, and anomaly detection.
- **Digital twins for simulation and testing:** Digital twins were frequently used to simulate various scenarios (cyberattacks, physical disruptions) enabling improved testing and preparation.
- **Blockchain for secure data management:** Some projects utilised blockchain for securing data and improving transparency in operations.

3.2. Transformations and trends introduced

The survey data highlights significant transformations and emerging trends shaping the future of critical infrastructure security. A key shift is the increasing reliance on and request of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), marking a move toward more proactive threat detection and response mechanisms. This technological evolution aligns with a broader trend of transitioning from static risk models to dynamic risk assessments, emphasizing real-time monitoring and adaptive strategies to address rapidly changing threats.

Collaboration and information sharing have also emerged as vital priorities, with respondents emphasizing the need for coordinated efforts across sectors and international borders to enhance security. Additionally, a focus on continuous monitoring indicates an evolution in cybersecurity architectures, suggesting a gradual alignment with zero-trust principles for more robust and adaptable defence mechanisms.

Despite these advancements, challenges persist, particularly around interoperability and the integration of diverse technologies. Addressing these issues will require developing improved solutions to ensure seamless system integration. Looking ahead, project coordinators foresee an increased focus on AI, quantum-resistant cryptography, and IoT security as key areas for innovation. Research into hyper-distributed applications is also recognized as a critical priority to meet future demands in securing interconnected infrastructures.

3.3. Technological challenges

The survey has highlighted several technological challenges faced by projects aimed at protecting critical infrastructure. These challenges span multiple domains, highlighting the complexity of implementing advanced technologies in this sector.

Data-related issues emerged as a significant hurdle, particularly concerning data availability and confidentiality. Many respondents reported difficulties in obtaining sufficient and high-quality data for training AI models or testing security solutions. The sensitive nature of the data, often subject to stringent privacy regulations in sectors like healthcare, further compounded the problem. Anonymization and synthetic data creation were suggested as potential solutions to overcome these barriers.

Integration and interoperability posed another layer of difficulty, especially when integrating modern technologies with legacy systems. Compatibility issues, mismatched data formats, and the need for

customized middleware solutions created significant obstacles. Additionally, ensuring seamless data exchange across diverse systems proved challenging, particularly in multi-technology environments.

Specific challenges related to AI and Machine Learning (AI/ML) included the need for large, high-quality datasets to train effective models and concerns about the accuracy and reliability of these systems. Incomplete or noisy/scattered data often led to suboptimal model performance, and reliance on specific data types for certain methodologies which further limit the applicability.

Other notable issues included restricted access to Operational Technology (OT) infrastructures due to regulatory and security constraints, as well as resource limitations, such as insufficient time, funding, or personnel, which hampered project progress.

Addressing these challenges will require a comprehensive approach, including improved data management practices, the development of advanced interoperability solutions, refinement of AI/ML methodologies, and stronger collaborative frameworks to facilitate data access and resource sharing.

Summary of key challenges:

Data-related challenges

- Insufficient availability of data for AI model training and testing.
- Restrictions on accessing confidential data in regulated sectors.

Integration and interoperability challenges

- Difficulties integrating new technologies with outdated legacy systems.
- Challenges ensuring interoperability across diverse systems and technologies.

AI/ML-specific challenges

- High demand for large, high-quality datasets for AI/ML models.
- Accuracy and reliability issues in AI/ML, particularly with incomplete or noisy/scattered data.

Other challenges

- Limited access to operational technology infrastructures for testing and validation.
- Resource constraints, including time, funding, and personnel shortages.

3.4. Industrial impact & market adoption

The industrial impact of the surveyed projects highlights their significant contributions across various critical infrastructure sectors. In the energy sector, projects focused on enhancing power grid resilience and security, utilizing digital twins for threat detection and simulation, and securing substations. Similarly, the transportation sector benefited from improved risk assessment and incident response capabilities, boosting system security and resilience. In the healthcare sector, tools were developed to protect sensitive data and respond to security threats effectively. The telecommunications sector saw advancements in monitoring and mitigation systems to safeguard networks, while the financial services sector implemented robust cybersecurity measures to secure financial systems and transactions. The water sector advanced in the protection of water infrastructure against physical and cyber threats by developing early-warning systems, risk management platforms, and secure communication tools. It also introduced scenario-based technical and organizational stress-testing platforms, enabling utilities to evaluate vulnerabilities, enhance

preparedness, and improve coordination during emergencies. These solutions enhanced the resilience and operational security of water systems, addressing the sector's growing reliance on digital transformation.

Additionally, many projects developed cross-sectoral tools such as risk management frameworks, threat simulation platforms, and interoperability solutions, applicable to multiple industries and domains of critical infrastructures. Market adoption of these innovations, however, varied. For many projects still in early development or piloting stages, market uptake is anticipated between 2025 and 2026. Pilot projects and demonstrations proved instrumental in showcasing the practical value of technologies, often securing early adopters and building trust with potential users. Collaboration with stakeholders, including industry partners and government agencies, was a key driver of adoption, ensuring alignment with market needs. Technologies at higher Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) exhibited higher adoption rates, as they were closer to being market ready. Effective marketing strategies, such as participation in industry events, publishing research, and offering training sessions, were employed to raise awareness and facilitate adoption.

Despite this progress, challenges remain, including integrating new technologies with existing systems, addressing data confidentiality concerns, and achieving widespread stakeholder buy-in. These barriers will need to be overcome to fully realize the market potential of these innovations.

Final summary:

- **Industrial applications:** Projects impacted critical infrastructure sectors such as energy, transportation, healthcare, telecommunications, water and financial services, with some tools applicable across multiple sectors.
- **Market adoption:**
 - Adoption varies widely, with many projects in early development or piloting phases, expecting broader uptake by 2025–2026.
 - Pilot demonstrations and strong stakeholder collaboration played pivotal roles in securing early adopters.
 - Technologies with higher TRLs experienced better adoption rates.
- **Strategies for uptake:** Effective dissemination through industry events, academic publications, training programs, and stakeholder partnerships boosted market readiness.
- **Challenges:** Integration with legacy systems, data confidentiality, and stakeholder alignment remain key barriers to adoption.

3.5. Legal & ethical considerations

The survey also outlines key legal and ethical considerations in the development of technologies for critical infrastructure security. In terms of **legal considerations**, data privacy and protection were the primary concerns, especially when handling sensitive data in regulated sectors such as healthcare. Many projects emphasized the need to navigate complex data protection regulations like the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** to ensure compliance with privacy laws. Intellectual property (IP) rights also emerged as a critical area, with specific focus on issues of ownership and licensing of newly developed technologies. Additionally, obtaining necessary access to and permissions for using critical infrastructure data for research and testing, posed legal challenges.

With regards to **ethics**, the responsible use of AI and machine learning algorithms was a central theme. Ethical concerns included the potential for **bias in AI algorithms**, with many projects recognizing the importance of rigorous testing to mitigate this issue. **Data privacy** and **transparency** were also emphasized, particularly regarding the privacy of individuals whose data was being used for research. To address these concerns, some projects employed the use of **anonymized or synthetic data**. Furthermore, there was a strong focus on ensuring **fairness and accountability** in AI-driven security systems, particularly with respect to AI-based decision-making. A broader concern was the **responsible use of technology**, ensuring that these advanced systems did not lead to unintended harmful consequences.

To manage these **legal and ethical challenges**, projects implemented various strategies. These included data anonymizations to remove personally identifiable information, ensuring **compliance with data protection regulations** like GDPR, and establishing **ethical review boards** to oversee research practices. Some projects also developed **ethical guidelines** or best practices for technology development and deployment. Emphasis was placed on **transparency** in data usage and decision-making processes, alongside ensuring accountability for the application of AI and other technologies.

In conclusion, the response stresses the importance of proactively addressing both **legal and ethical challenges** when developing and implementing technologies for critical infrastructure security. This involves careful attention to **data privacy, regulatory compliance**, and the **responsible use of AI**, with various strategies in place to mitigate risks and ensure that legal and ethical standards are met throughout the process.

Final summary:

- **Legal considerations:** Key concerns included data privacy, protection regulations (such as GDPR), intellectual property rights, and access to critical infrastructure data.
- **Ethical considerations:** These focused on bias in AI, data privacy, transparency, fairness, accountability, and the responsible use of advanced technologies in security applications.
- **Management strategies:** Implemented strategies such as data anonymization, compliance with regulations, establishing ethical review boards, developing ethical guidelines, and ensuring transparency and accountability in AI and data use.

4. Regulatory, Ethical and Standards Development

To shed light on the current situation about regulations, ethics and standards, the EU-CIP project prepared two specific surveys.

The **EU CER Directive on the Resilience of Critical Entities** survey was conducted to assess the preparedness and resilience of critical infrastructure across EU member states. As this directive focuses on entities that provide essential services, it shall contribute that they can withstand and recover from a wide range of disruptions, including natural disasters, cyberattacks, and other emergencies. The survey aimed to identify vulnerabilities, evaluate existing measures, and recommend improvements to enhance security and continuity of the critical services.

The **EU Legal, Ethical, and Standardisation Frameworks** survey was carried out to evaluate the alignment of EU laws, ethical guidelines, and standardisation practices in the typical emerging fields such as artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and data protection. As technological innovation accelerates, there is a pressing need to ensure that these advancements are guided by robust ethical

principles and legal frameworks that safeguard human rights, privacy, and security. The survey was aimed to highlight gaps, overlaps, and inconsistencies within current frameworks, providing insights to help harmonise regulations and encourage responsible development and deployment of new technologies across the EU.

4.1. Survey about the EU CER Directive on the Resilience of Critical Entities

The EU-CIP project plays an important role in supporting the implementation of the CER Directive by fostering collaboration, advancing technological innovation, and developing policy recommendations for critical infrastructure resilience. Recognising the importance of engaging stakeholders across the CIP/CIR ecosystem, the project conducted a targeted survey to assess familiarity with the Directive, identify implementation challenges, and gather actionable recommendations to inform future research, technology, and policy actions.

This sub-section presents an analysis of the CER Directive survey conducted within the EU-CIP project. It outlines the goals of the survey, summarises the key findings from the responses, and provides structured recommendations for advancing research, technology, and policy to address the challenges and gaps identified. Additionally, the chapter offers a forward-looking perspective on the role of the EU-CIP project in enhancing critical infrastructure resilience and supporting the successful implementation of the CER Directive.

The survey, still open at http://eucip2.eu-vri.eu/Survey_Run.aspx?ID=1040 and its results will be analysed in detail separately in a dedicated report. The reporting below is an intermediate one, based on the data available at the time of 2nd project conference (Nov. 13, 2024) in Madrid, Spain.

The survey included 15 questions covering:

- Participants' profile (3 questions, mandatory).
- Participants' familiarity with the CER Directive (5 questions, mandatory).
- Participants' views about the challenges related to the implementation of the Directive (2 questions).
- Participants' views about possible enhancements of the Directive (4 questions).
- Participants' final comments (1 question, some input mandatory).

The preliminary/intermediate evaluation below includes primarily "raw" statistical data, as obtained from the multiple choice and similar questions.

The final evaluation will

- Link the statistical (quantitative) results with the comments provided by the responders (qualitative inputs).
- Include subsequent important inputs (e.g. from the US).
- Provide analysis among different responders' groups.
- Analyse representativeness of the results and identify and analyse possible biases (e.g., representation of lack of single countries or certain types of stakeholders).

4.1.1. Goals of the survey

The CER Directive survey was conducted as part of the EU-CIP project to achieve the following objectives:

- **Assess Familiarity with the CER Directive:** Gauge the knowledge and understanding of the Directive among critical infrastructure stakeholders and the broader "EU resilience community."
- **Identify Implementation Challenges:** Explore the main difficulties and concerns related to implementing the Directive at both national and EU levels.
- **Gather Recommendations:** Collect insights and suggestions for improving the Directive's application, including potential R&D, policy, and technological actions.
- **Inform Policy Recommendations:** Use the survey results to shape actionable recommendations to enhance critical infrastructure resilience.

4.1.2. Intermediate results of the survey

The survey received responses from **over 60 stakeholders**, with insights reflecting a diverse cross-section of the CIP/CIR ecosystem. The geographical distribution of survey respondents shows a diversity of countries, providing insights into the varying participation of stakeholders. Responses were received from a wide range of countries, including European nations like Greece, Italy, Germany, as well as non-European entities such as Taiwan and Jordan. This distribution highlights the global interest and engagement in critical infrastructure resilience, with strong representation from European nations, reflecting the Directive's EU focus, alongside contributions from international stakeholders (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of survey participants amongst EU member states.

4.1.2.1. Respondent Profiles

- **Sectors Represented:**
 - Predominant sectors include Energy, Transport, and Digital Infrastructure.
 - Underrepresented sectors are Health and Wastewater, suggesting gaps in engagement with certain critical entities.
- **Roles in CIP/CIR:**
 - A significant portion of respondents were involved in R&D, consulting, and education/training.
 - Fewer participants were from Regulatory bodies and CI operators, indicating limited engagement from entities directly responsible for operational resilience. This limited representation points to a need for increased engagement from entities directly responsible for operational resilience and regulatory oversight.

The respondent profile highlights robust involvement from sectors and roles focused on innovation and knowledge dissemination. However, the underrepresentation of certain sectors and operational roles underscores the necessity for targeted outreach and engagement strategies. Ensuring a balanced representation across all critical sectors and roles is essential for the effective implementation of the CER Directive. This balanced engagement will facilitate comprehensive resilience planning and foster a unified approach to safeguarding Europe's critical infrastructures.

4.1.2.2. Familiarity with the CER Directive

- **Awareness Levels:**
 - Approximately 21% of respondents demonstrated detailed familiarity with the CER Directive.
 - Over 50% had limited or no knowledge of the Directive, a concerning gap given its relevance.
- **Familiarity with Related Directives:**
 - Higher awareness was given for NIS2, GDPR, and Seveso, reflecting a stronger familiarity with cybersecurity and industrial safety frameworks.

The disparity in awareness levels suggests a need for targeted educational initiatives to elevate understanding of the CER Directive. Leveraging the existing familiarity with related directives, stakeholders can draw parallels to the CER Directive, facilitating a more integrated approach to compliance and resilience planning. Enhancing awareness is crucial for the Directive's successful implementation, ensuring that all relevant entities are prepared to meet its requirements and contribute to a more resilient infrastructure landscape across the EU.

4.1.2.3. Implementation Challenges

The survey identified several key challenges and gaps in the implementation of the EU Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive:

- **Key Challenges Identified:**
 - **Common Resilience Metrics, Sensitive Data, and Information Sharing** (61%). A significant portion of respondents highlighted difficulties in establishing standardized resilience metrics. The handling of sensitive data and the complexities of information sharing among entities were also major concerns.
 - **General Complexity and Administrative Burden** (58%). The Directive's comprehensive requirements are perceived as complex, leading to concerns about increased administrative workloads and the potential for bureaucratic inefficiencies.
 - **Threat, Risk, and Resilience Assessment** (over 50%). Challenges were noted in effectively assessing threats, risks, and resilience, indicating a need for improved methodologies and tools in these areas.
- **Gaps in implementation:**
 - Limited clarity on roles of competent authorities and single points of contact (SPoCs).
 - Poor understanding of transposition deadlines, with over half unaware of the October 2024 deadline.

4.1.2.4. Possible Support from Research Projects for the Implementation and Further Development of the CER Directive

The survey also explored areas where research projects could provide support to facilitate the implementation and advancement of the CER Directive. Respondents indicated a need for research and development (R&D) support in several key areas. The following examines how R&D initiatives can effectively address these challenges, focusing on practical solutions and frameworks to facilitate compliance, foster innovation, and build a robust culture of resilience across critical infrastructure sectors. The survey highlights specific challenges where R&D projects can significantly contribute to the implementation and enhancement of the EU CER Directive. An analysis of these challenges and recommendations on how R&D efforts can address them effectively is provided.

General Challenges: Complexity of Requirements, Administrative and Operational Burden

Respondents highlighted the need for research to simplify the Directive's requirements and reduce administrative burdens. Developing streamlined processes and clear guidelines through research initiatives could facilitate more efficient implementation.

R&D role:

- **Development of simplified frameworks:** R&D can support the creation of modular, easy-to-use tools and methodologies to guide critical entities in understanding and implementing the directive's requirements.
- **Automated administrative tools:** Design of digital platforms for automating compliance reporting, reducing administrative burdens for critical entities and competent authorities.
- **Sector-Specific guidance:** Tailor frameworks to address the unique operational contexts of different sectors outlined in the CER Directive.

Challenges related to common resilience metrics, sensitive data, and information sharing

There is a strong demand for research focused on establishing standardised resilience metrics and developing frameworks for the secure handling and sharing of sensitive information. Such efforts are considered crucial to address the complexities identified in these areas.

R&D Role:

- **Standardization of Resilience Metrics:** Identify and establish universally applicable metrics for assessing and improving resilience across sectors, ensuring comparability and consistency.
- **Secure Data Sharing Mechanisms:** Research secure and privacy-preserving systems for sharing sensitive information between critical entities, national authorities, and EU institutions.

- **Integration Platforms:** Develop interoperable platforms to facilitate real-time data sharing during emergencies, ensuring compliance with both CER and NIS2 directives.
- **Innovative Data Sharing Platforms:** Research into blockchain and other distributed ledger technologies for secure and transparent information exchange.
- **AI-Driven Insights:** Leverage AI to analyse shared data for identifying patterns, forecasting risks, and suggesting resilience measures.
- **Cross-Directive Synergies:** Ensure alignment between CER and NIS2 requirements for cyber and non-cyber risks.

Challenges Related to Harmonization and Standardization

Respondents emphasized the need for harmonized resilience frameworks across Member States and sectors. Variations in national regulations and sector-specific practices create inconsistencies that complicate the Directive's implementation. Standardization efforts are essential to ensure uniformity and interoperability across critical infrastructure systems.

R&D Role:

- **Pan-European Standards:** Collaborate with standardization bodies to develop EU-wide technical standards for resilience measures, enabling uniform implementation across Member States.
- **Cross-Sectoral Interoperability:** Research compatibility between existing national frameworks and EU-level standards to avoid duplication or conflicts.
- **Best Practices Repository:** Develop a dynamic repository of successful resilience practices from Member States and sectors to promote learning and standardization.

Challenges Related to the Impact on Innovation, Human Resources, and New Expertise Needed

Stakeholders identified the need to balance the Directive's resilience requirements with fostering innovation, especially for smaller entities with limited resources. Moreover, a shortage of skilled professionals and expertise poses significant challenges in meeting the Directive's technical and operational demands, underscoring the importance of workforce development and capacity building.

R&D Role:

- **Capacity Building:** Develop training programs and certifications for stakeholders in critical sectors to ensure workforce readiness.
- **Innovation-Friendly Compliance Tools:** Research and develop compliance solutions that balance the need for resilience with the flexibility required for innovation, especially for SMEs.
- **Promoting Multidisciplinary Expertise:** Encourage cross-sectoral research to integrate engineering, social sciences, and policy for holistic resilience strategies.

Challenges Related to Threats, Risks, and Resilience Identification & Assessment (Essential Support)

Accurately identifying and assessing threats, risks, and resilience measures is a critical challenge for implementing the Directive. The dynamic nature of threats, particularly cross-sectoral and cross-border risks, necessitates advanced tools and methodologies to ensure comprehensive risk assessments and proactive resilience strategies.

R&D Role:

- **Advanced risk assessment models:** Develop predictive tools and methodologies for identifying emerging threats, using AI and big data analytics.
- **Scenario simulations:** Design systems for modelling cascading risks and cross-sectoral dependencies to prepare for complex crises.
- **Dynamic risk frameworks:** Ensure adaptability of risk assessment methodologies to evolving threat landscapes.

R&D projects can play a key role in ensuring the successful implementation of the CER Directive while fostering a culture of resilience and innovation across the EU.

4.1.2.5. Additional Support for the enhanced implementation of CER Directive

The implementation of the EU CER Directive faces several challenges that require targeted research and support to ensure its success. This analysis highlights key areas where R&D efforts and additional EU supporting documents can address critical gaps and enhance resilience across Member States.

EU Supporting Documents for Chapters III and IV

The survey underscores a significant demand for EU-level supporting documents to enhance the implementation of the CER Directive, particularly in relation to **Chapter III: Resilience of Critical Entities** and **Chapter IV: Critical Entities of Particular European Significance**. Respondents highlighted a widespread lack of familiarity and expertise in these areas, reflecting the need for comprehensive guidance. For Chapter III, supporting documents could provide detailed frameworks and methodologies for conducting resilience assessments, developing resilience plans, and implementing effective mitigation strategies. Similarly, for Chapter IV, such documents could clarify the roles and responsibilities of critical entities with transnational importance, as well as provide best practices for managing cross-border risks and dependencies. These materials would not only address the knowledge gaps identified by stakeholders but also promote a more uniform and effective application of the Directive across Member States. Additionally, the documents could serve as foundational resources for training and capacity-building initiatives to empower entities and authorities with the tools and knowledge needed to fulfil their obligations under the Directive.

The survey revealed that over **50% of respondents** felt unqualified to address key chapters of the EU CER Directive. This lack of confidence likely stems from several factors, including the complexity and novelty of the Directive, insufficient sector-specific guidance, and limited access to training or resources tailored to the Directive's requirements.

4.1.2.6. Perspectives on Enhancements

- Over 75% supported explicitly addressing "polycrises" which involve multiple critical infrastructures.
- Strong demand for systemic frameworks integrating cross-sector dependencies and advanced simulation tools for stress testing.

The survey revealed a strong consensus among respondents on the need to enhance the CER Directive by explicitly addressing complex, interconnected crises, commonly referred to as "polycrises." Over 75% of participants advocated for the Directive to incorporate provisions that consider the cascading effects and interdependencies among multiple critical infrastructures. This perspective aligns with recent discussions emphasizing the importance of understanding and mitigating the entanglement of crises across global systems¹.

Some answers in the survey provided the reasoning behind the decision to leave the specification of threats outside the scope of the Directive.

Additionally, there was a significant demand for the development of systemic frameworks that integrate cross-sector dependencies. Respondents highlighted the necessity for advanced simulation tools capable of stress-testing these interdependencies to assess vulnerabilities and enhance resilience. Such tools are crucial for modelling the complex interactions between different infrastructure sectors and for preparing effective response strategies².

These insights underscore the pressing need for a holistic approach regarding the Directive, one that not only addresses individual sectoral risks but also considers the broader, interconnected nature of modern critical infrastructures. By incorporating these enhancements, the Directive can better equip entities to anticipate, withstand, and recover from multifaceted crises that span multiple sectors.

4.1.2.7. Final Comments

Stakeholders specifically highlighted the importance of standardised risk assessment tools, sector-specific resilience plans, and robust incident notification systems to effectively implement the EU Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive. Focusing on these areas is essential for the successful implementation of the CER Directive. By prioritizing uniform risk assessments, customized resilience planning, and efficient incident communication, stakeholders can strengthen the resilience of critical entities across the EU.

4.1.3. R&D actions – recommendations

Based on the survey results, the following research and development actions are recommended:

¹ https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/global-sustainability/article/global-polycrisis-the-causal-mechanisms-of-crisis-entanglement/06F0F8F3B993A221971151E3CB054B5E?utm_source=chatgpt.com

² https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-51043-9_2?utm_source=chatgpt.com

- **Develop standardised tools:** Create methodologies and digital platforms for conducting comprehensive risk assessments and modelling cascading risks across critical sectors.
- **Adapting to dynamic threat environments:** One challenge is ensuring that resilience measures are adaptable to the rapidly changing threat landscape. This could require ongoing updates to risk assessments and the development of flexible resilience strategies that can evolve alongside the project. Invest in R&D to create flexible resilience strategies and tools that can evolve accordingly.
- **Balancing innovation with security requirements:** Like other directives, the CER Directive could potentially impose constraints on innovation if not carefully implemented. R&D projects may struggle to balance the need for security and resilience measures with the flexibility needed for innovation. This is particularly true for (smaller) entities that may lack the resources to fully comply with the directive without compromising their innovative capacity. Approaches of research have to harmonise the directive's security and resilience measures with the flexibility needed to foster innovation, particularly for smaller entities.
- **Integration with existing frameworks:** Many entities already operate under various regulatory frameworks, such as those related to data protection (GDPR) or sector-specific regulations. Integrating CER requirements with these existing frameworks pose administrative challenges. Streamlining compliance processes to avoid duplication of effort and conflicting requirements will be critical. Studies must be conducted to streamline compliance by aligning CER requirements with existing regulations like GDPR, NIS2, and sector-specific frameworks.
- **Support cross-sector analysis:** Investment in tools and research to address dependencies between critical infrastructures in polycrisis scenarios has to be taken. Whereas sector-specific challenges have to be analysed and tailored solutions must be proposed.
- **Cross-border coordination:** CER encourages cooperation among Member States through the Critical Entities Resilience Group, which can help share best practices and information. Research models to enhance cooperation among Member States, leveraging the Critical Entities Resilience Group for best practices and shared resources.
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** As the Directive is implemented, it will be important to monitor its impact and effectiveness. This could involve regular reviews of how entities are complying with the Directive, the effectiveness of resilience measures in real-world incidents, and the overall impact on the security and continuity of critical services. Feedback from these evaluations can then inform future updates to the Directive or the development of additional support measures. Methods for monitoring the effectiveness of resilience measures and compliance with the Directive in real-world scenarios must be developed.
- **Enhance resilience metrics:** Clear and adaptable resilience metrics to monitor and improve the resilience of critical entities must be established.
- **Innovate training programs:** Training materials and simulations to improve familiarity with the CER Directive, particularly among underrepresented sectors must be designed.

4.1.4. Technology development actions – recommendations

Some recommendations are given below to enhance the technological foundation of the CER Directive implementation:

- **Risk assessment tools:** To comply with the CER Directive, critical entities will need to conduct thorough risk assessments. Developing standardized tools and frameworks for these assessments would be highly beneficial. These tools could help organizations identify vulnerabilities, assess the likelihood and impact of potential threats, and develop appropriate mitigation strategies. For instance, a digital platform that consolidates data on past incidents, emerging threats, and risk scenarios could be useful in helping entities conduct more accurate and comprehensive assessments.
- **Coordination mechanisms:** The directive emphasizes the importance of collaboration between various entities and authorities. Establishing or strengthening coordination mechanisms at both national and EU levels will be crucial. This could involve the creation of dedicated communication channels, joint task forces, or regular coordination meetings to share information, resources, and best practices. Create dedicated communication tools, such as secure platforms for real-time information exchange, joint task forces, or coordination systems for national and EU-level collaboration.
- **Resilience plans:** Entities must create resilience plans that outline measures to prevent, respond to, and recover from incidents. Providing templates and guidelines for these plans can facilitate compliance and ensure consistency across sectors.
- **Incident notification systems:** Establishing robust systems for incident notification. Entities need to report incidents to competent authorities within 24 hours, followed by a detailed report within a month.
- **Digital twins and simulation tools:** Promote the development of digital twins for infrastructure systems to simulate disruptions and test resilience strategies.
- **Incident notification systems:** Standardize technologies for rapid incident reporting, ensuring alignment with the Directive's requirements.
- **Secure data sharing platforms:** Facilitate sensitive data exchange and information sharing among critical entities, leveraging advanced encryption and privacy-preserving technologies.
- **Automation for compliance:** Invest in tools that streamline compliance processes, such as automated resilience plan generation and monitoring.

4.1.5. Policy actions – recommendations

Policy measures should complement technological and R&D efforts:

- **Policy briefs:** Develop detailed policy briefs at national and EU levels to clarify Directive requirements and address sector-specific challenges.
- **Guidance and clarification:** Policy briefs at both the national and EU levels could play a significant role in guiding the implementation of the CER Directive. These briefs can provide

detailed explanations of the directive's requirements, sector-specific advice, and case studies illustrating successful resilience strategies. They can also address common challenges and misconceptions, helping entities better understand their obligations and how to meet them.

- **Support for smaller entities:** Policy briefs could be particularly useful for smaller entities that may lack the resources or expertise to navigate the complexities of the directive. By offering practical advice and potentially highlighting funding opportunities or technical support options, policy briefs could help level the playing field and ensure that all entities, regardless of size, can effectively enhance their resilience.
- **Promoting best practices:** Regularly updated policy briefs could serve as a platform for sharing best practices across the EU. By showcasing successful strategies and innovations in resilience, these documents could encourage a culture of continuous improvement and proactive risk management among critical entities.
- **Training and awareness programs:** Effective implementation will require extensive training for both public and private sector stakeholders. These programs should cover the specifics of the directive, best practices in risk management, and incident response strategies. The complexity of threats, particularly in areas like cybersecurity, necessitates specialized training for staff at all levels of an organization.
- **Competent authorities and SPoCs:** Strengthen coordination mechanisms between competent authorities and SPoCs to ensure effective implementation and reporting.
- **Funding mechanisms:** Provide financial incentives and grants for smaller entities to meet Directive requirements without compromising innovation.
- **Integrated frameworks:** Ensure coherence between the CER Directive and related EU policies, such as NIS2 and GDPR, to reduce regulatory overlaps.

4.1.6. Conclusions and future outlook

The CER Directive represents a pivotal opportunity to enhance the resilience of critical entities across the EU. However, its implementation requires a holistic approach combining R&D, technology development, and policy actions. The CER Directive survey has provided valuable insights into current awareness, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. The following broader context and strategic considerations are provided:

- **Long-term cultural change:** The directive is not just about compliance but about fostering a culture of resilience across the EU. This requires a shift in how critical entities approach security and risk management. Rather than seeing these as secondary concerns, they need to be integrated into the core planning and operational processes. This cultural shift will take time and will require sustained effort from both regulators and industry leaders. EU funded projects could play an important role in this direction.
- **Alignment with other EU initiatives:** The CER Directive should be seen in the context of other EU initiatives aimed at enhancing security and resilience, such as the Network and Information Systems (NIS2) Directive or the EU Cybersecurity Strategy. Ensuring coherence and synergy between these frameworks will be essential for avoiding overlaps and contradictions. For R&D projects, particularly those that are cross-border or involve multiple

sectors, aligning CER requirements with these other initiatives will help streamline compliance and maximize the impact of resilience efforts.

- **Monitoring and evaluation:** As the directive is implemented, it will be important to monitor its impact and effectiveness. This could involve regular reviews of how entities are complying with the directive, the effectiveness of resilience measures in real-world incidents, and the overall impact on the security and continuity of critical services. Feedback from these evaluations can then inform future updates to the directive or the development of additional support measures.

These findings from the survey as well as the insights on the impact to Policy, as the CER directive, of AI systems in critical infrastructure resilience will guide the EU-CIP project's ongoing efforts to enhance the resilience of critical entities and ensure the successful implementation of the CER Directive.

4.2. Survey about EU Legal, Ethical and Standardisation frameworks

4.2.1. Goals of the survey

The primary objective of the survey was to gather insights from diverse stakeholders on the current state of the European Union's legal, ethical, and standardisation frameworks in the domain of CIP and CIR. To achieve this, the survey focused on several key areas.

Firstly, it aimed to assess stakeholder knowledge by evaluating their understanding of key EU regulatory frameworks, including the NIS2 Directive, the CER Directive, and the EU Cybersecurity Act. This assessment also sought to identify gaps in knowledge and areas requiring further clarification or training. Secondly, the survey examined the practical challenges stakeholders face when applying these frameworks within their organizations and sectors. This included understanding the ease or difficulty of implementation and identifying specific barriers such as overlapping regulations, inconsistencies, or sector-specific issues.

Another important focus of the survey was to explore ethical considerations within the CIP/CIR sector. It examined the extent to which ethical frameworks guide decision-making and aimed to highlight areas where stakeholders require additional ethical guidance or support. The survey also evaluated familiarity with standardisation by assessing stakeholders' knowledge of standardisation processes, bodies, and mechanisms. This evaluation aimed to identify areas where further standardisation is needed to enhance interoperability, risk management, and data protection.

Finally, the survey prioritized actions for improvement by collecting stakeholder views on the most critical areas for regulatory, ethical, and standardisation enhancements. The insights gathered were intended to inform actionable recommendations for research, technology, and policy development under the EU-CIP project. By addressing these goals, the survey aimed to establish a foundation for actionable recommendations, fostering improved alignment between technological advancements, ethical considerations, and regulatory compliance in CIP and CIR across the EU.

4.2.2. Results of the survey

The survey gathered insights from 14 stakeholders across academia, industry, public institutions, and standardisation bodies to evaluate their understanding and application of EU legal, ethical, and standardisation frameworks in CIP and CIR. The number of participants in the survey is modest, considering that the cut-off sample size in social research is $N=30$, but it still allows for drawing certain conclusions. Diverse representation highlights the multifaceted nature of CIP and CIR, emphasizing the need for collaboration across technical, ethical, regulatory, and operational dimensions. The variety of roles and expertise among participants underscores that challenges in this domain are not confined to specific sectors but demand a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach for effective solutions.

Figure 5: Distribution of survey participants amongst EU member states.

The country distribution chart reflects the participation of respondents from various nations, primarily within Europe, with Germany contributing the largest share at 20%, Spain and the United Kingdom follow with 13.3% each, while there is equal representation (6.67%) from France, Finland, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, and Norway. Additionally, the inclusion of Korea (6.67%) underlines the global relevance of EU frameworks, signalling interest from non-European stakeholders in understanding or adopting similar approaches. 6.67% of "Unassigned" responses suggests broader international or cross-border engagement, with participants potentially opting to remain anonymous. Overall, this geographic diversity emphasizes the collaborative nature of CIP and CIR efforts, requiring input from multiple nations and sectors to develop comprehensive and effective strategies.

4.2.2.1. Understanding of the EU Regulatory framework

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
■	Very Good	8	57.14 %	■	Poor	1	7.14 %
■	Average	5	35.71 %	■	No answer	0	0.00 %

Figure 6: Understanding of the EU regulatory framework amongst survey participants.

The survey revealed varying levels of understanding among respondents regarding the EU regulatory frameworks (the EU regulatory framework for CIP/CIR considered refers to the EU NIS2 Directive, the CER Directive and the EU Cybersecurity Act). A significant proportion of respondents indicated a strong understanding of the EU regulatory framework. Specifically, 57% of respondents rated their understanding as "Very Good," while 36% reported their knowledge as "Average". Only 7% admitted their understanding was "Poor". These results suggest that while many stakeholders feel confident in their grasp of the regulatory landscape, significant gaps remain for a portion of respondents.

Respondents with lower ratings cited specific challenges in fully understanding the frameworks. These included the complexity of overlapping national and EU regulations, difficulties in interpreting specific compliance requirements, and a need for greater familiarity with recent updates to directives such as NIS 2 and CER. One respondent noted: "While I have a foundational understanding of the EU regulatory framework for Critical Infrastructures Protection..., I recognize that there are areas where my knowledge could be deeper. Specifically, I could benefit from a more detailed grasp of recent updates, practical implementations, and specific compliance requirements within each directive...." This feedback underscores the need for initiatives aimed at improving accessibility, clarity, and sector-specific guidance for the EU regulatory framework.

4.2.2.2. Application of the EU Regulatory Framework:

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
Blue	Easy	2	14.29 %	Red	Difficult	4	28.57 %
Yellow	Average	8	57.14 %	Dark Blue	No answer	0	0.00 %

Figure 7: Participant's answers about ease of application of EU regulatory framework.

When asked about the ease of applying the EU regulatory framework in their work, only 14% of respondents found it "Easy". A majority, 57%, rated it as "Average," while 29% found it "Difficult". This signals significant barriers to practical implementation. The challenges cited included overlapping regulations, unclear distinctions between national legislation and EU directives, and the additional burden of sector-specific requirements. For instance, respondents from the aviation sector pointed out that existing regulations often overlap with new directives, requiring careful mapping to ensure compliance. Smaller organizations also reported limited resources and expertise to navigate these frameworks effectively.

4.2.2.3. Evaluation of Regulatory Framework Comprehensiveness

Figure 8: Answers rating the comprehensiveness of the EU regulatory framework.

The survey shows a generally positive assessment of the comprehensiveness of EU regulatory frameworks. A significant majority (71%) of respondents rated the frameworks as "Comprehensive," while 29% considered them "Relatively Comprehensive". No respondents rated the frameworks as "Not Comprehensive," suggesting broad acknowledgment of the frameworks' depth and scope. However, respondents also identified areas where the frameworks could be improved. Some pointed out that the regulatory texts, while detailed, often leave room for interpretation, which can complicate uniform application across sectors. Overlaps between various EU regulations, such as the NIS 2 Directive, the Digital Services Act, and the Cyber Resilience Act, were noted as sources of confusion and inefficiency. These findings underline the importance of clearer guidelines and harmonized implementation strategies to enhance the usability and effectiveness of the frameworks across diverse sectors.

4.2.2.4. Ethical Considerations

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
Blue	Yes	3	21.43 %	Red	Not really	4	28.57 %
Yellow	Need More Guidance	7	50.00 %	Dark Blue	No answer	0	0.00 %

Figure 9: Answers on application of ethical frameworks in CIP/CIR.

The survey highlighted significant gaps in the adoption and application of ethical frameworks within the CIP/CIR sector. Regarding ethical framework, only 21% of respondents indicated they follow a defined ethical framework in their decision-making processes. Meanwhile, 50% stated they need more guidance on ethical matters, and 29% reported not using any ethical framework at all. Key challenges identified included balancing privacy, transparency, and security in decision-making, particularly in the context of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI). Respondents noted the absence of tailored ethical guidelines specific to the CIP/CIR domain, which would help bridge the gap between regulatory compliance and practical implementation. These findings highlight the need for the development of sector-specific ethical frameworks and tools to support stakeholders in navigating complex ethical dilemmas while aligning with EU legal and regulatory standards.

a) Challenges in ethical decision making

When asked if they had faced ethical dilemmas in their work, some respondents mentioned dilemmas such as balancing Privacy vs. Security in incident reporting, and Transparency vs. Confidentiality when sharing vulnerabilities under the NIS2 Directive. For example, organizations often grapple with whether disclosing vulnerabilities may expose them to exploitation or harm trust among stakeholders. Others highlighted challenges in integrating emerging technologies, like artificial intelligence (AI), into critical systems without violating ethical principles such as fairness or accountability.

Several respondents admitted to not encountering ethical dilemmas due to adherence to regulatory frameworks. However, some pointed out the lack of clarity or tailored ethical guidance for specific contexts, such as AI-driven systems or operator data in critical environments. These findings underscore the importance of creating clearer and more actionable ethical guidelines specific to the CIP/CIR domain.

b) Ethical and regulatory priorities for the EU-CIP project

When asked which regulatory or ethical frameworks should be prioritized by the EU-CIP project, respondents provided a range of suggestions, highlighting key areas of focus. The

importance of focusing on the CER Directive was emphasized due to its relevance in addressing critical infrastructure challenges. Others highlighted the need to address compatibility and discrepancies between various frameworks, particularly in the context of national implementations of the NIS Directive, suggesting a focus on simplifying processes for critical infrastructure operators. The AI Act was also identified as a priority, reflecting concerns about the ethical and regulatory challenges posed by artificial intelligence in critical systems.

Some respondents suggested exploring the interplay between ethical frameworks and regulations, such as aligning compliance between the ALTAI (Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence) and the EU Cybersecurity Act. This was accompanied by calls to integrate principles from the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) to ensure alignment with broader ethical and human rights considerations. Additionally, sector-specific concerns, such as public health risks and the ethics of data processing using technical operator data, were highlighted as pressing areas for focus.

Respondents also suggested prioritizing ethical theories relevant to technological applications, such as consequentialism, deontological ethics, and virtue ethics, though noting their misalignment with regulations like GDPR. The need to integrate dynamic risk assessment for emerging technologies such as cloud computing and autonomous systems was emphasized, alongside aligning ethical considerations with frameworks such as the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) and NIS2 Directive. Finally, some participants recommended a comprehensive analysis of all existing frameworks to harmonize them and focus on practical compliance strategies, particularly in areas like data privacy, transparency, and balancing security with public interest. These varied responses reflect the complexity and interdisciplinary nature of regulatory and ethical challenges in CIP and CIR.

4.2.2.5. Familiarity with Standardisation

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
Blue	Not familiar	1	7.14 %	Red	Very familiar	6	42.86 %
Yellow	Moderately familiar	7	50.00 %	Dark Blue	No answer	0	0.00 %

Figure 10: Participant's answers about familiarity with standardisation.

Respondents displayed diverse levels of familiarity with standardisation processes. A significant portion (43%) described themselves as "Very Familiar," indicating a strong understanding of standardisation frameworks and practices. Another 50% of participants reported being "Moderately Familiar," reflecting some experience but highlighting opportunities for further engagement. Only 7% of respondents admitted to being "Not Familiar," suggesting that knowledge of standardisation is generally well-distributed across stakeholders.

a) Familiarity with standardisation mechanisms

Figure 11: Participant's familiarity with processes and mechanisms of standards.

When asked about their understanding of the processes and mechanisms involved in standardisation, respondents displayed varying levels of familiarity. A majority (57%) of participants rated their understanding as "Moderately," while 43% described their understanding as "Very Well." Notably, all respondents provided an answer, indicating active engagement and interest in the topic. This distribution suggests that while many stakeholders have a solid grasp of standardisation processes, there remains room for improvement in deepening understanding across the board. The relatively high percentage of those with "Moderately" good understanding highlights an opportunity to provide targeted training and resources to bridge gaps in expertise and further empower stakeholders to contribute effectively to standardisation initiatives.

b) Mechanisms for contributing to standardisation

Figure 12: Participant's perception of mechanisms contributing to standardisation.

Respondents demonstrated a strong familiarity with various mechanisms for contributing to standardisation efforts. Working groups and technical committees were the most recognized mechanisms, with 86% of respondents indicating familiarity. These results highlight the collaborative nature of standardisation efforts and the role of these groups in driving critical discussions and decisions. Public consultations were familiar to 64% of respondents, reflecting active engagement in providing feedback on draft standards or regulatory proposals. Pre-standardisation activities, such as early-stage exploratory efforts, were noted by 57% of participants, indicating moderate engagement in foundational discussions prior to formal standardisation. Other mechanisms were identified by 7% of respondents, with one participant specifically referencing standardisation mandates related to specific regulations.

The high familiarity with working groups and technical committees underscores their importance as central platforms for stakeholder collaboration in standardisation. However, the relatively lower awareness of pre-standardisation activities suggests an area where additional outreach and education could enhance participation. These findings reflect the active role stakeholders play in shaping standardisation efforts, while also identifying opportunities to broaden involvement in earlier stages of the process.

c) Priority areas for standardisation

Figure 13: Participant's expectations for being key areas for standardisation.

The survey results indicate that risk assessment and management is the most critical area requiring standardisation contributions, with 93% of respondents identifying it as a top priority. This reflects the importance of developing harmonized frameworks to assess and mitigate risks effectively across sectors and regions. It underscores the need for consistent methodologies to address evolving threats to critical infrastructures. Incident response and management was highlighted by 64% of respondents, emphasizing the need for standardised protocols to improve preparedness, coordination, and recovery efforts during incidents. Similarly, data protection and privacy, and interoperability of systems were each identified by 50% of participants, signalling the necessity of creating robust standards to safeguard sensitive data and ensure seamless interaction between diverse systems.

Additionally, 21% of respondents proposed other critical areas, such as data sharing, lifecycle management and supply chains, and contributions from CEN/TC 391 on Societal and Citizen Security. These suggestions reflect the complexity of addressing emerging challenges in CIP/CIR, including the need for transparency and efficiency in data handling, secure supply

chain practices, and the integration of societal considerations into standardisation efforts. These findings highlight the multidimensional approach required to enhance critical infrastructure resilience through targeted standardisation initiatives.

d) Importance of aligning EU-CIP activities with existing standardisation mechanisms

Figure 14: Participant's opinion of EU-CIP alignment with other standardization mechanisms.

The survey results underscore the importance of aligning the EU-CIP project's activities with existing standardisation mechanisms. Most respondents (57%) rated this alignment as "Very Important", emphasizing the critical need for consistency and integration with established frameworks to ensure coherence and efficiency in standardisation efforts.

Another 43% of participants rated this alignment as "Moderately Important", suggesting that while alignment is significant, there may also be room for flexibility to address unique or emerging challenges that existing mechanisms may not fully cover. Notably, all respondents provided an answer to this question, reflecting widespread recognition of the relevance of this issue. These results highlight that a majority of stakeholders see the alignment as essential for fostering interoperability, avoiding duplication of efforts, and ensuring that the EU-CIP project complements rather than conflicts with existing initiatives.

4.2.2.6. Stakeholder expectations and engagement with EU-CIP standardisation initiatives

a) Expected value of the EU-CIP project in standardisation

Figure 15: Participant's understanding of EU-CIP's contribution to standardisation.

Results highlight the diverse ways in which respondents expect the EU-CIP project to contribute to standardisation. The most anticipated contribution is participation in working groups, with 93% of respondents identifying this as a key value. This reflects the importance of collaborative platforms for discussing and shaping standards, where the EU-CIP project can have a significant impact by providing expertise and representation.

Involvement in technical committees was the second-highest expectation, cited by 71% of respondents. This underscores the need for the EU-CIP project to engage directly in the formal processes where standards are developed and finalized. Additionally, 57% of respondents emphasized the importance of engagement in public consultations, demonstrating a demand for inclusive and transparent processes that consider a wide range of stakeholder inputs.

Other areas of expected value include the initiation of pre-standardisation activities (50%), where the project can lead early-stage exploratory work to identify gaps and propose solutions, and the provision of tailored standardisation support (29%), which reflects a more targeted need for guidance and resources specific to stakeholders' operational contexts.

b) Preferred standardisation services and materials from the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub

Figure 16: Expected standardisation services/material from EU-CIP Knowledge Hub.

Respondents identified several types of standardisation services and materials that would be most beneficial from the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub. The most valued resource was case studies and best practices, selected by 93% of respondents. This highlights the importance of practical examples and proven approaches that stakeholders can directly apply to their work in CIP/CIR. Documentation and guidelines were the second most preferred resource, cited by 86% of participants. This reflects the need for clear, concise, and accessible materials to support the interpretation and implementation of standards across various sectors. Training and workshops were highlighted by 57% of respondents, emphasizing the importance of capacity-building initiatives to enhance skills and understanding of standardisation processes. Finally, consultation services, selected by 36% of participants, indicate a demand for tailored support to address specific challenges or contexts in implementing standards.

These findings suggest that stakeholders prioritize actionable insights, practical guidance, and opportunities for skill development as the most beneficial offerings that the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub should provide. By focusing on these areas, the Knowledge Hub could effectively support stakeholders in advancing standardisation efforts and improving resilience in critical infrastructure.

a) Frequency of utilising EU-CIP Knowledge Hub standardisation resources

Color	Name	Value	Percent	Color	Name	Value	Percent
Blue	Never	2	14.29 %	Red	Very frequently	5	35.71 %
Yellow	Occasionallly	7	50.00 %	Dark Blue	No answer	0	0.00 %

Figure 17: Participant’s perception how often they use EU-CIP resources.

The survey results indicate varying levels of anticipated engagement with standardisation resources provided by the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub. Most respondents (50%) stated they would use the resources “Occasionallly”, suggesting that while these materials are valued, they might be accessed on a need-based or project-specific basis. 36% of participants indicated they would utilise the resources “Very frequently”, reflecting a core group of stakeholders who view the Hub as an essential tool for their work in standardisation. Conversely, 14% of respondents noted they would “Never” use the resources, likely due to their specific roles or contexts where such materials may not be directly relevant.

These findings highlight the importance of ensuring that the Knowledge Hub offers diverse, high-quality, and easily accessible resources to cater to both occasional and frequent users. The Hub can also explore targeted outreach to engage potential users who may currently see limited applicability of these resources.

4.2.3. Summary of findings and path ahead

The survey results provide valuable insights into the current state of legal, ethical, and standardisation frameworks for CIP&CIR. They highlight several key challenges and opportunities that must be addressed to strengthen these frameworks and enhance their application across various sectors.

A significant conclusion from the survey is the diverse levels of understanding and application of EU regulatory frameworks among stakeholders. While many respondents demonstrated a good grasp of these frameworks, substantial gaps were noted, particularly in navigating the overlap between national and EU-level regulations. This issue is further compounded by the complexity of sector-specific requirements, which smaller organizations find especially challenging. Addressing these gaps requires practical guidance, harmonized directives, and tailored training programs to enhance the accessibility and usability of these frameworks.

The findings also underscore the underdevelopment of ethical frameworks in the CIP/CIR domain. Only a small proportion of stakeholders currently follow defined ethical guidelines in their decision-

making processes. Many respondents highlighted the absence of sector-specific ethical resources, which are crucial for addressing complex dilemmas, particularly those introduced by emerging technologies such as AI. This points to an urgent need for actionable and tailored ethical frameworks that balance considerations such as privacy, security, and transparency.

In terms of standardisation, stakeholders identified risk assessment, incident management, data protection, interoperability, and lifecycle management as critical areas for contributions. The strong familiarity with mechanisms like working groups and technical committees demonstrates stakeholders' active involvement in shaping standards. However, there is a noticeable opportunity to enhance participation in pre-standardisation activities, which are vital for fostering innovation and identifying gaps in the early stages of standard development.

The EU-CIP Knowledge Hub should emerge as a key Hub for addressing these challenges. Respondents emphasized the value of case studies, practical documentation, and capacity-building workshops as the most beneficial resources the Hub could offer. However, the survey also revealed varied engagement levels, with many stakeholders accessing these resources only on a project-need basis. This suggests the importance of creating resources that are not only high-quality and actionable but also adaptable to diverse user needs.

Moving forward, the EU-CIP project should focus significantly on harmonizing and simplifying regulatory directives to reduce barriers to implementation. This involves aligning national and EU-level directives and creating tools that map overlapping frameworks to provide greater clarity. Developing comprehensive ethical frameworks tailored to the unique challenges of CIP/CIR, including those posed by AI and data privacy concerns, could also be essential. Strengthening stakeholder engagement in standardisation, particularly in early-stage activities, will further enhance collaboration and innovation. Expanding the offerings of the Knowledge Hub to include more accessible and practical resources will support long-term engagement and capacity-building.

In conclusion, the EU-CIP project is well-positioned to address these challenges and drive meaningful advancements in CIP and CIR. By fostering collaboration, providing practical tools, and aligning ethical, regulatory, and standardisation practices, the project can ensure that CI in the EU remains robust, secure, and resilient against evolving threats.

4.3. Relevance of the AI Act and use of intelligence in Critical Infrastructures

4.3.1. Overview

The **AI Act** holds significant relevance for the deployment of AI technologies within critical infrastructures, particularly as these systems become increasingly integrated into essential services. This legislation provides a regulatory framework that addresses the ethical and safety concerns associated with AI applications. As critical infrastructures, such as energy, transportation, and telecommunications, leverage AI for enhanced operational efficiency, compliance with the AI Act will be crucial in mitigating risks related to data privacy, security, and algorithmic bias. The act's emphasis on transparency and accountability guides organizations in developing AI systems that comply with legal standards and foster public trust in automated processes.

The integration of AI is destined to significantly alter operational models within critical infrastructures. The convergence of AI with emerging technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT)

and big data analytics is expected to transform how these systems are monitored and managed. For example, AI-driven predictive maintenance can minimize downtime by anticipating failures before they occur, thereby enhancing service continuity. However, organizations must approach this integration cautiously, ensuring that their AI systems are designed with robust ethical frameworks to prevent unintended consequences stemming from automated decision-making processes.

Moreover, the implementation of the **Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive** underscores the importance of resilience in critical infrastructures amidst increasing cyber threats and natural disasters. The AI Act complements this directive by ensuring that AI technologies deployed in these sectors are resilient and capable of adapting to dynamic environments. As organizations strive to enhance their resilience strategies, they must also focus on aligning their AI initiatives with regulatory requirements. This alignment not only aids in compliance but also enhances overall operational resilience by safeguarding vital services against disruptions.

4.3.2. AI's resilience challenges

Despite its benefits, AI also introduces several challenges that need to be addressed, including:

- **Adversarial attacks against AI systems:** The increased deployment of AI systems provides malicious actors with a new set of vulnerabilities that they can exploit. Specifically, AI systems are vulnerable to various adversarial attacks that can compromise their effectiveness, such as:
 - Poisoning Attacks, which involve injecting malicious data into a model's training set towards altering its behaviour and reducing its accuracy or compromising its operation during deployment.
 - Evasion Attacks, which involve attackers that subtly modify inputs to deceive AI models into misclassifying data. This can lead to unauthorized access or data breaches.
 - Inference Attacks, which aim to extract sensitive information from AI models by probing them with different inputs.
- **Generative AI systems robustness and reliability:** The popular generative AI systems, including large language models (LLMs), present their own challenges, including:
 - **Hallucinations:** LLMs can generate outputs that are incorrect or nonsensical but appear plausible. These "hallucinations" pose risks in contexts where accuracy is important, which is typically the case for AI systems that protect critical assets.
 - **Lack of explainability:** The complexity of LLMs and other Generative AI models makes it difficult to understand their decision-making processes. This results in a lack of transparency that can hinder trust and accountability, as well as compliance with the mandates of European regulations such as the AI Act.
 - **Prompt engineering attacks:** LLMs are also susceptible to prompt engineering attacks, which are launched in order to manipulate the models' outputs by crafting specific inputs, often referred to as prompt injections. These attacks exploit the models' reliance on the prompts they receive to generate responses, potentially leading to unintended or harmful outcomes. Some common types of prompt engineering attacks, include: (i) Jailbreaking i.e., overwriting or revealing the underlying system prompt to bypass safety features and generate harmful or unauthorized content and (ii) Instruction Manipulation i.e., instructing the model to ignore its original programming and follow new, potentially harmful instructions.

These challenges make CI operators cautious against adopting and fully leveraging AI as an integral part of their critical infrastructure resilience strategies.

Beyond adversarial attacks, CI operators and security integration must address additional challenges, notably challenges in the following areas:

- **Skills gap:** There is a significant skills gap in effectively using AI tools. Therefore, CI operators need to invest in training programs to equip their workforce with the necessary skills to operate and manage AI systems.
- **Data modernization:** High-quality data is essential for effective AI deployments. Unfortunately, the availability of properly structured and quality digital data from CIs cannot be taken for granted. CI Operators must invest in data modernization infrastructures to ensure that their datasets are accurate, comprehensive, and up to date.
- **Investment in infrastructure:** Deploying AI at scale requires substantial investment in AI infrastructures, including AI hardware, software, middleware and tools. This implies a need for additional investments that must be undertaken by CI operators and security organizations.

These additional challenges raise the complexity and cost of AI deployments. Hence, they lead CI operators in factoring and balancing the various trade-offs that are associated with AI-based deployments for critical infrastructure resilience.

4.3.3. AI's Policy impact on the Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive

The challenges and opportunities of AI systems in critical infrastructure resilience have a policy impact as well, notably an impact on the recent CER Directive of the European Union. CER is designed to enhance the resilience of critical infrastructure across various sectors towards ensuring the uninterrupted provision of essential services. The directive addresses a wide range of risks, including natural disasters, cyber threats, and other hazards. The integration of AI into this framework has significant implications on how these objectives are achieved, including positive and negative implications. The positive side includes:

- **AI's potential for enhanced risk assessment and management**, which can improve the risk assessment processes that are mandated by the CER Directive. Specifically, the directive includes a requirement for regular risk assessments and the development of resilience plans, which can be more effectively supported based on AI.
- **AI's promise for increase automation and efficiency**, which can lead to quicker and more efficient handling of disruptions. This is very important for meeting the CER Directive's obligations for incident notification and response within tight timeframes.
- **Use of AI analysis for cross-border cooperation**, in response to CER's mandate for cross-border cooperation among EU Member States. AI facilitates this based on advanced data analysis tools that enable better sharing and interpretation of information across borders. This can lead to more coordinated responses to threats that affect multiple EU countries.
- **Compliance with AI regulations**, as any AI integration in critical infrastructures must comply with the AI Act. This influences how AI systems are deployed under the CER Directive. High-risk AI systems used by critical entities must align with internal risk management processes as

outlined in the AI Act and the CER Directive. This ensures that AI applications do not introduce new vulnerabilities while enhancing resilience.

- **AI-supported technical and organizational measures**, including measures required by the CER Directive. For instance, AI can be used to optimize security protocols, manage access controls, and ensure continuous monitoring of critical systems.

On the other hand, the downside (i.e., the negative impacts of AI on CER implementation) includes:

- **Increased cyber threats**, as AI systems can introduce new vulnerabilities for critical infrastructures.
- **Intensified skills gap**, which complicates the implementation of CER mandates.

and asks for additional upskilling and cross-training of CI operators' security staff.

- **AI's potential for misuse**, as AI can be also exploited by malicious actors. For instance, generative adversarial networks (GANs) can be used to develop and launch sophisticated cyberattacks.
- **High stakes of system failures**, as AI-enabled systems in critical infrastructures rely on big data and interconnected networks. This can lead to high stakes if these systems fail.

5. Outcomes from the 2nd Annual Conference of the EU-CIP Project

The 2nd EU-CIP Annual Conference, titled "Resilience Reimagined: Innovating Critical Infrastructure for Tomorrow," took place on November 13, 2024, in Madrid as part of the Critical Infrastructure Protection Week. The event brought together policymakers, industry leaders, academics, and innovators to address emerging challenges and opportunities in critical infrastructure resilience. Discussions centred on *implementing the EU's Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive* and *fostering innovation to enhance the security of vital services*. Key activities included expert panels, focus group discussions, and networking sessions, emphasizing collaboration to bridge policy gaps and support infrastructure modernization.

The conference also highlighted cutting-edge solutions from the EU-CIP "Innovators' Pool" and unveiled resources like the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub to facilitate ongoing knowledge exchange across Europe.

5.1. Innovative Policies, Resilient Infrastructures

The roundtable discussion at the second EU-CIP Annual Conference, titled "Innovative Policies, Resilient Infrastructures: A policy Dialogue" gathered crucial experts to explore the challenges and opportunities in protecting critical infrastructure amidst a rapidly evolving geopolitical and technological landscape.

Paolo Venturoni, CEO of the European Organisation for Security, highlighted the deteriorating geopolitical scenario and the heightened risk of state-sponsored cyber-physical attacks on European infrastructures, stressing the need for swift and coordinated action.

Gerd Müller from SECUNET advocated for the establishment of a European Security Fund, as outlined in EOS's recent position paper, to comprehensively address research and deployment in critical infrastructure protection, with particular emphasis on emerging technologies like Quantum Key Distribution.

Monica Cardarilli from the JRC underscored the CER Directive's shift from traditional protection to a resilience-focused approach, advocating for harmonized resilience strategies across the EU.

Sandra Mezzadri from IABG echoed the need for ambitious security programs, pointing out that adapting defence-oriented capability development approaches to the security domain requires substantial financial backing to meet strategic goals.

The discussion also underscored the critical role of innovation and collaboration in tackling current and future challenges. David Luengo from INDRA called for the EU to move beyond compliance-driven frameworks, urging a focus on development and deployment to address security gaps effectively.

Jorge Bernal Bernabe from the RESILMESH project emphasized the importance of cyber situational awareness, with AI-based anomaly detection systems playing a pivotal role in identifying threats.

Aljosa Pasic from the SUNRISE project reflected on lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the need for adaptability in policy and operations, as well as the inclusion of frontline practitioners in the regulatory process.

Luis Simon from the VUB added an international perspective, advocating for alignment between EU and US regulations to enhance collective security.

The session concluded with a shared understanding that advancing critical infrastructure resilience demands strategic investment, cross-sectoral collaboration, and a forward-looking approach that leverages cutting-edge technologies and harmonized policies across Europe.

5.2. Aligning Current Innovations with Practitioners' Needs in Critical Infrastructure

The Focus Group Discussions at the EU-CIP Annual Conference provided an interactive platform to align current innovations with the practical needs of critical infrastructure practitioners. Moderated by experts in respective sectors, these sessions delved into challenges and opportunities across transport, energy, health technologies, ICT, finance, regarding resilience and security of critical infrastructures. Participants included policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and critical infrastructure operators, ensuring a well-rounded exchange of insights.

Each group addressed sector-specific issues as described below:

The **Transport group**, moderated by Tim Stelkens-Kobsch (DLR), explored the integration of AI/ML technologies to enhance resilience in critical infrastructure, emphasizing the importance of a clear regulatory framework to address emerging threats. Participants highlighted the need for AI solutions to support, rather than replace, human decision-making in critical areas like air traffic control and healthcare. They stressed that AI must provide decision support and not decisions, ensuring that human expertise remains central while leveraging AI's capabilities for resilience.

The group also discussed the interplay between the CER and NIS2 directives, noting that while these frameworks offer protections for users, they do not directly safeguard critical infrastructure itself. To address this gap, participants called for new regulations to define context-specific risks, improve innovation pathways, and tackle AI-related liabilities, such as those involving UAVs and autonomous technologies. Clear accountability in AI-driven decisions was identified as a priority, with participants emphasizing the need for regulations to address liability in cases of system failures or accidents. The session underscored the importance of regulatory clarity and innovation to enhance resilience in the evolving transport sector.

The **Energy group**, moderated by Frédéric Guyomard (EDF), delved into the critical interconnection between climate risks and cybersecurity, emphasizing the urgent need for governance clarity, certification, and proactive resilience strategies. Participants noted the challenges in aligning safety and cybersecurity governance under the CER Directive, highlighting the importance of accessible and reliable data for effective risk management and disaster preparedness. The discussion underscored the compounding risks of climate-induced vulnerabilities and cyber-attacks, with a strong emphasis on the energy sector's reliance on NIS2-mandated coordinated approaches for digital resilience and physical infrastructure protection.

The group also explored the directive's broader implications, including the necessity of multidisciplinary teams to address overlapping resilience and cybersecurity concerns. Key measures such as enhanced equipment monitoring, improved IoT security, supply chain certification, and the adoption of climate-focused ISO standards were identified as priorities. To successfully implement these directives, participants stressed the importance of staff training, top management awareness, and dedicated teams combining expertise in both physical and digital risk management. The session highlighted the importance of harmonizing national directive implementations and the need for standardized frameworks to ensure comprehensive energy sector resilience.

The **Health Technologies group**, moderated by Miguel Gaspar (ULS), focused on balancing innovation with privacy and security while addressing the modernization needs of healthcare IT systems. Discussions emphasized the critical importance of data sovereignty and clear AI liability regulations to build trust and mitigate risks like LLM hallucinations and non-human errors. Participants highlighted the necessity for healthcare organizations to actively engage in policymaking to ensure regulations reflect practical needs.

The group also discussed challenges in adopting innovative technologies due to outdated software and systemic inertia, proposing modernization of healthcare IT systems and simplified processes for integrating EU-funded solutions. Interoperability and scalability were identified as priorities to streamline infrastructure and enhance system customization during healthcare unit mergers. The session concluded with a "healthcare trilemma" framework emphasizing decentralization, robust security, and scalability to drive resilient, adaptive, and secure healthcare systems.

The **Finance group**, moderated by Ramon Martín de Pozuelo (CXB), focused on overcoming the challenges of long-term sustainability for innovations, aligning resilience efforts with the Digital Operational Resilience Act, and enhancing threat intelligence sharing. Discussions highlighted the "Valley of Death" for innovations, where transitioning from EU-funded projects to private sector adoption often fails due to limited commercial viability or utility for operators. Participants emphasized the need for stronger exploitation frameworks, better testing infrastructure for financial critical infrastructures, and collaboration with agile FinTechs.

The group also addressed DORA compliance, underscoring the importance of strengthening security for third-party providers and implementing standardized certifications for supply chains. Threat intelligence sharing was identified as a critical area, with a call for an EU-specific platform to complement existing solutions like FS-ISAC. Additionally, resilience metrics, vendor risk assessments, and crisis simulations were highlighted as essential tools to ensure robust operational integrity in financial services. The session concluded with actionable recommendations to bridge gaps in innovation adoption, regulatory alignment, and collaboration across the financial ecosystem.

The **Resilience and Safety group**, moderated by Gabriele Giunta (ENG), examined the integration of the CER and NIS2 directives, focusing on regulatory harmonization and cascading responsibilities to enhance critical infrastructure resilience. Participants highlighted the overlapping scopes of the directives and challenges in resource allocation, information sharing, and stakeholder awareness. Case studies from Germany and Lombardy, Italy, showcased diverse approaches, such as integrating directives into national frameworks and fostering cross-border collaboration through voluntary operator participation.

The group also addressed the need for standardized practices to harmonize safety and security procedures while mitigating risks. Concerns around private operators' reluctance to report incidents, due to business integrity issues, were juxtaposed with the benefits of open data for improving infrastructure safety. Recommendations emphasized the development of clear, harmonized frameworks, fostering public-private cooperation, and aligning best practices to ensure interoperable data sharing and enhanced resilience across critical infrastructure sectors.

Finally, the **ICT group**, moderated by Ioan Constantin (Orange Romania), explored the dual role of AI in enhancing ICT resilience while introducing new risks. Participants emphasized AI's ability to detect and counter threats through advanced models like LLMs while addressing the challenges of compliance with the evolving EU AI Act and existing cybersecurity regulations. The group highlighted the need for stronger frameworks to bridge regulatory gaps and ensure standardization to minimize vulnerabilities in AI deployment.

The discussion also covered supply chain risks, emphasizing the importance of securing hardware and software components, particularly those involving open-source elements. Participants pointed out geopolitical and regulatory complexities that impact the integrity of supply chains, calling for robust certification processes and collaboration across EU stakeholders. The session concluded with a call to strengthen EU-level frameworks, promote standardization, and adopt proactive risk management strategies to secure ICT systems against emerging threats.

These discussions fostered cross-sectoral collaboration, identifying gaps and actionable recommendations. Moderators summarised their findings in the conference's concluding session, providing strategic insights to guide future innovations and policy development in critical infrastructure protection.

5.3. EU-CIP “Own innovators’ pool”

The EU-CIP “Own Innovators’ Pool” session at the 2nd EU-CIP Annual Conference showcased a diverse group of innovators who are at the forefront of developing solutions aimed at enhancing critical infrastructure protection. This session featured nine presenters, each a winner from the recent [EU-CIP Open Call Type B](#), who shared their innovative approaches to addressing the challenges faced by critical infrastructures across Europe.

The session began with **Spiros Chadoulos** from Plegma Labs who presented **cloud.gr**, an IoT platform that enhances the resilience of critical infrastructures by providing real-time data analytics and monitoring capabilities. Spiros emphasized how this technology can empower organizations to make informed decisions that bolster their operational resilience against various threats.

Next, **Roman Schotten**, founder of Adaptlantis from Germany, discussed his solution focused on flood management. He outlined how his approach identifies and prioritizes action areas while developing concrete proposals to enhance the resilience of critical infrastructure networks against flooding events. Roman's insights underscored the necessity of proactive measures in disaster management.

The presentations continued with **José Antonio Cabo Valdés** from Libelium in Spain, who showcased an IoT solution aimed at improving energy efficiency within Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs). The IoT solution highlights the role of technology in optimizing energy consumption and reducing operational costs while maintaining service reliability.

Boris Petrenj, Senior Researcher at Politecnico di Milano, introduced the **Business Continuity Game (BCG)**—an online simulation-based serious game designed for engaging business continuity training. This innovative approach emphasizes the importance of preparedness and training in ensuring organizations can effectively respond to disruptions.

Eleni Kamateri from INFALIA presented **ImproveMyWater**, a web-based Decision Support System for early warning and response in water utilities. The system aims to enhance water quality management and ensure timely responses to potential issues, thereby safeguarding public health.

Dr. **Dionysios Nikolopoulos** from Tethys Consulting introduced the **PROCRUSTES platform**, an integrative scenario-based stress-testing platform for advanced strategic and tactical cyber-physical resilience of water distribution systems. His presentation highlighted how this platform can increase preparedness against complex scenarios of attack including cascading effects and facilitate

decision making as well as collaboration among stakeholders in enhancing cyber-physical systems' resilience.

Next, **Vasileios Mavroeidis** from Cyentific AS presented a ground-breaking application for generating, maintaining, storing, retrieving, exchanging, and digitally signing standardised cybersecurity operations playbooks in a no-code graphical manner. This innovation aims to simplify cybersecurity processes and enhance operational efficiency across various sectors.

Finally, **Lazar Dašić** from the University of Kragujevac in Serbia shared his work on a Business Intelligence (BI) tool utilising artificial intelligence to assess and improve the resilience of critical infrastructure in industrial applications. His insights into AI's role in resilience planning were particularly noteworthy.

The EU-CIP “Own Innovators’ Pool” session showcased cutting-edge CIP solutions but also fostered valuable discussions about future collaborations among innovators and stakeholders in critical infrastructure protection.

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6. Analysis of EU-CIP sectorial White Papers

As part of its mission, EU-CIP has so far produced six sector-specific white papers that provide detailed analyses of key vulnerabilities, emerging risks, current gaps, and strategic opportunities across critical sectors, including Water, Energy, Finance, Space, Telecommunications, and Transport. Five additional white papers are in progress, covering Health, Public Administration, Banking, Maritime, and a second paper on the Water sector.

This analysis focuses on the six white papers already published. The upcoming papers will also be examined further in the context of the remaining roadmaps (D3.9 and D3.10) and published in the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub ([Whitepapers – Knowledge Hub](#)).

- **Water sector:** The water sector is critical to society and the economy, but it faces significant challenges in addressing the growing sophistication of cyber and physical attacks. Historically, the sector has focused more on physical than cyber security, which leaves vulnerabilities in its integrated cyber-physical systems. Workforce shortages, limited situational awareness, and the convergence of physical and cyber systems exacerbate these challenges. The STOP-IT project emphasized the importance of defence-in-depth mechanisms and advanced risk management approaches to address cyber and physical threats effectively.
- **Energy sector:** The energy and electricity sectors are targeted as they become more digitized and networked, increasing the attack surface due to interdependencies with other facilities. Threats such as Advanced Persistent Threats (APT), ransomware, and sabotage highlight the need for enhanced security measures. Coordinated responses to hybrid threats are crucial, with the CER and NIS2 directives supporting resilience and risk mitigation. A secure European Energy Data Space is critical for ensuring privacy-preserving data exchange and operational security in interconnected energy grids.
- **Finance sector:** The financial sector is experiencing rapid digitalization, which, while improving efficiency, increases exposure to cyberattacks such as ransomware, phishing, and advanced social engineering attacks. Emerging technologies like Large Language Models (LLMs) and blockchain are creating both opportunities and vulnerabilities. The sector is also impacted by regulatory developments such as the CER Directive and the EU's Digital Finance strategy. Enhanced cyber-physical threat intelligence systems and compliance with regulatory frameworks are essential to ensure resilience against evolving hybrid threats.
- **Space sector:** The space sector is increasingly a target of hybrid threats, particularly affecting satellite ground segments. Physical attacks disrupt satellite data distribution, while cyberattacks compromise data integrity and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) standards. Innovative solutions, including e-fences, passive radars, and multimedia AI technologies, have been developed under the 7SHIELD project to enhance cyber-physical security. Aligning global practices and leveraging advanced technologies will be essential to building resilience in this sector.
- **Telecommunications sector:** The telecommunications sector faces significant challenges due to rapid digitalization and interconnectivity. Key threats include cyberattacks on cloud computing, data centres, and physical infrastructure such as fibre-optic networks and wireless towers. The adoption of a Zero Trust approach, improved OT (Operational Technology) security, and collaborative threat intelligence frameworks are critical. To maintain resilience, regulatory policies must balance the need for innovation with robust security measures.

- **Transport sector:** The transport sector relies heavily on GNSS for navigation, making it highly vulnerable to disruptions. As climate change exacerbates risks, the need for resilient infrastructure has become increasingly critical. The integration of IoT and AI enables real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, which can mitigate risks and enhance operational efficiency. Backup navigation systems and robust cybersecurity measures are essential for ensuring continuity. Regulatory frameworks must address cross-sectoral dependencies to prevent cascading failures and bolster resilience.

These white papers serve as a foundation for understanding the unique challenges faced by each sector while highlighting cross-sectoral dependencies that could amplify cascading failures. More sectors will be covered, and other sectorial white papers will be released in the context of EU-CIP project.

A central pillar of the EU-CIP approach is the integration of data-driven analysis and foresight extraction. The project identifies actionable insights and future trends that are critical for shaping policy, guiding innovation, and ensuring the sustainability of Europe's critical infrastructures. The insights from these white papers not only inform sector-specific strategies but also contribute to the overarching goal of harmonising resilience and security measures across the European Union. This analysis allows easy identification of gaps and overlaps between related documents thus providing an aggregated and consolidated overview of current knowledge, as well as in the current policy landscape. Moreover, a trend analysis is generated and extrapolated for extracting foresight about CIP/CIR, including: (i) Notable changes in the CIP/CIR technological, innovation and policy landscape; (ii) Technological, scientific and research megatrends; (iii) Representative/reference scenarios for protecting assets and infrastructures in various sectors; and (iv) Consolidated ideas about the future evolution of policies, standards, technologies, and research results.

6.1. Analysis based on major keywords

The analysis of the white papers focuses on some keywords specifically related to Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR), namely:

- Cybersecurity,
- Resilience,
- Vulnerability,
- Threat,
- Risk,
- Infrastructure,
- Technology,
- Policy,
- Innovation,
- Security.

The first step of the analysis is to determine the frequency of these keywords in each white paper. The detailed keyword frequency analysis for each document in the given sectors is illustrated in table below:

Table 1: Keyword frequency analysis for each white paper in the given sectors

Sector	Cybersecurity	Resilience	Vulnerability	Threat	Risk	Infrastructure	Technology	Policy	Innovation	Security
Telecommunications	1	4	4	34	5	38	8	3	6	19
Transport	5	9	2	31	10	59	5	0	6	9
Finance	16	20	5	6	15	41	17	2	10	63
Water	23	3	3	22	32	18	10	1	7	42
Space	7	13	2	33	27	56	59	25	41	65
Energy	26	12	1	41	8	36	5	2	17	47
Total	78	61	17	167	97	248	104	33	87	245

The keyword analysis reveals key thematic priorities and trends across the EU-CIP white papers, emphasising the interconnected challenges and opportunities within CIP/CIR.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure is the dominant theme, reflecting the centrality of physical and digital systems in all sectors. The significant focus highlights the importance of understanding interdependencies between critical infrastructures such as Telecommunications, Energy, and Transport. The interconnected nature of infrastructures necessitates cross-sectoral strategies to address cascading risks and ensure continuity of operations during disruptions.

Security

Security emerges as a critical priority, particularly in Finance (63 mentions) and Space (65 mentions). These sectors face increasing challenges from hybrid threats, cyberattacks, and data integrity issues. Sectors are placing emphasis on strengthening both cybersecurity and physical security measures to mitigate complex threats and vulnerabilities.

Risk

Risk is a recurring theme, with high mentions in Water (32) and Space (27). These sectors face unique risks due to climate change and geopolitical factors, necessitating advanced predictive tools and risk mitigation frameworks. Developing robust risk assessment methodologies and integrating real-time data are key to addressing sector-specific and cross-sectoral vulnerabilities.

Threat

The prominence of threats in the analysis reflects growing concerns about hybrid threats, including cyberattacks, physical disruptions, and cascading failures. Energy (41) and Telecommunications (34) lead this category, underlining their vulnerability to evolving threat vectors. Addressing hybrid threats requires coordinated defence strategies that integrate cyber-physical risk management tools.

Technology and innovation

The Space sector leads in mentioning technology (59 mentions), driven by advancements in satellite systems and AI integration. Innovation is a key focus in Finance (10) and Space (41), where blockchain, AI, and digital twins are reshaping operations. Investing in emerging technologies is critical for enhancing resilience, operational efficiency, and adaptive capabilities across sectors.

Resilience

Resilience, particularly in the Finance (20) and Space (13) sectors, reflects the need for adaptive systems that withstand cyber and physical disruptions. This aligns with the goals of the CER and NIS2 directives. Resilience strategies should focus on both proactive measures (e.g., stress-testing) and reactive mechanisms (e.g., recovery protocols) to minimize downtime and societal impact.

Policy

Despite its low count, policy alignment is a cross-sectoral priority, with mentions tied to EU directives like CER and NIS2. Sectors such as Telecommunications (3) and Energy (2) highlight the need for regulatory frameworks to drive harmonization. Greater emphasis on policy integration can enhance compliance, standardization, and cross-border collaboration.

Cybersecurity and vulnerability

Cybersecurity appears most prominently in Energy (26) and Finance (16), reflecting the rising threat of ransomware, phishing, and APTs in these sectors. Vulnerability is less frequently mentioned but remains critical in sectors like Water (3) and Transport (2). Cybersecurity investments and vulnerability assessments are crucial to safeguarding interconnected systems from sophisticated threats.

The interplay of security, infrastructure, and risk underscores the need for holistic risk management frameworks. Technology and innovation drive progress, but challenges like interoperability and regulatory compliance must be addressed. The focus on resilience aligns with the objectives of EU directives, ensuring a harmonized approach to CIP and CIR. This analysis reflects a strategic shift towards integrating advanced technologies, enhancing interdependency management, and aligning policies to address an increasingly complex threat landscape.

6.1.1. Sector-Specific Trends

Some **sector-specific trends** are analysed:

- **Telecommunications sector:** The main trend is related to growing threats to Interconnected Networks. The high occurrence of "Threat" (34 mentions) and "Infrastructure" (38 mentions) underscores the sector's vulnerability to hybrid threats targeting 5G networks, fibre-optic lines, and cloud computing systems. The focus on "Cybersecurity" (1 mention) highlights the emerging need for advanced security frameworks tailored to rapidly expanding networks. The main direction in this sector seems to be the enhanced adoption of **Zero Trust Architecture** and collaborative threat intelligence sharing to safeguard interconnected assets.
- **Transport sector:** The main trend is related to the increasing dependency on GNSS and Resilience Challenges. "Infrastructure" (59 mentions) and "Risk" (10 mentions) indicate the sector's reliance on satellite navigation systems and the critical need to address disruptions. "Resilience" (9 mentions) highlights the growing focus on climate-adaptive infrastructure to counter extreme weather impacts. The main direction in this sector seems to encourage the investments in **backup navigation systems** and **IoT-driven predictive maintenance** to ensure operational continuity.

- **Finance sector:** The main trend is related to balance Innovation and Cybersecurity. High occurrences of "Security" (63 mentions), "Cybersecurity" (16 mentions), and "Innovation" (10 mentions) reflect the sector's dual focus on integrating technologies like blockchain and defending against sophisticated threats like ransomware and phishing. This aligns with its regulatory-heavy environment and exposure to cyber risks like ransomware and fraud. This indicates a strong focus on cybersecurity measures, technological advancements, and infrastructure security. High frequency of "innovation" indicates a forward-looking approach, likely due to the rapid adoption of AI, LLMs, and blockchain technologies in this sector. "Policy" (2 mentions) indicates a growing need to align innovation with compliance frameworks such as CER and the EU Digital Finance Strategy. The main direction in this sector seems to encourage the deployment of **AI-driven fraud detection** and enhanced regulatory alignment to secure digital financial ecosystems.
- **Water sector:** The main trend is related to address Physical and Cyber Risks simultaneously. The dominance of "Risk" (32 mentions) and "Security" (42 mentions) signals the sector's focus on managing both physical vulnerabilities and emerging cyber threats in IoT-enabled systems. "Resilience" (3 mentions) and "Technology" (10 mentions) reflect the push for advanced tools like real-time monitoring and situational awareness platforms. The main direction in this sector seems to encourage the adoption of **defence-in-depth strategies** and EU-wide water security governance models to improve resilience.
- **Space sector:** The main emphasis is on technological advancement and resilience. "Technology" (59 mentions) and "Innovation" (41 mentions) dominate the discourse, highlighting the sector's push towards advanced solutions like satellite virtualization, Earth Observation systems, and AI integration. High mentions of "Threat" (33 mentions) and "Risk" (27 mentions) underscore concerns about hybrid threats targeting satellite ground stations and data security. The main direction in this sector underlines the focus on **cyber-physical security frameworks**, FAIR data principles, and international regulatory harmonization to strengthen resilience.
- **Energy sector:** The main trend is on rising Hybrid Threats and operational challenges. The prominence of "Cybersecurity" (26 mentions), "Threat" (41 mentions), and "Infrastructure" (36 mentions) reflects the sector's struggle with advanced persistent threats (APT) and cascading risks. The lower focus on "Policy" (2 mentions) suggests a gap in aligning operational measures with evolving regulatory frameworks like CER and NIS2. The main direction in this sector seems to encourage the integration of **real-time security assessment tools** and the establishment of a **European Energy Data Space** for secure and collaborative operations.

6.1.2. Cross-Sectoral Insights

- **Hybrid threat resilience:** Sectors like Energy, Space, and Telecommunications are prioritising hybrid threat mitigation, indicating a need for integrated cyber-physical security solutions.
- **Technological integration:** Space and Finance lead in adopting cutting-edge technologies, while Transport and Water are leveraging IoT and AI for infrastructure resilience.

- **Policy alignment:** Sectors show varying levels of regulatory alignment, with Telecommunications and Finance demonstrating the strongest ties to directives like CER and NIS2.
- **Risk and interdependency management:** High mentions of "Infrastructure" and "Risk" across all sectors reflect the criticality of managing cascading risks in interconnected systems.

6.2. Current Gaps in the analysed sectors

Critical infrastructures are the backbone of modern society, ensuring the provision of essential services such as energy, water, transport, telecommunications, finance, and space-based systems. However, these infrastructures face escalating risks from hybrid threats, aging systems, climate change, and the increasing complexity of interconnected networks. To safeguard their functionality and enhance resilience, it is vital to conduct a thorough analysis of sector-specific and cross-sectoral gaps. This analysis, derived from a comprehensive review of the EU-CIP sectoral white papers, identifies critical vulnerabilities, systemic weaknesses, and operational challenges across key domains. By pinpointing these gaps, the findings serve as a foundation for developing actionable recommendations and guidelines to strengthen Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR). The subsequent section outlines the key findings for each sector, emphasizing the urgency of addressing these gaps to ensure sustainable and secure infrastructure operations across Europe.

6.2.1. Energy Sector

The Energy Sector white paper identifies several key gaps in the context of cybersecurity, resilience, and operational integrity, emphasizing the need for enhanced measures to protect against both physical and cyber threats:

Fragmented cybersecurity efforts

Cybersecurity measures are often fragmented across different regulations and sectors, leading to inconsistent implementation and significant vulnerabilities. This fragmentation complicates coordination and leaves critical infrastructure exposed to sophisticated cyberattacks such as APTs (Advanced Persistent Threats).

Limited real-time security systems

Current security systems lack real-time integration with operational systems, including SCADA and OT environments. The absence of dynamic risk assessment tools makes it challenging to detect and respond to evolving threats in a timely manner.

Insufficient interoperability and coordination

Challenges exist in ensuring interoperability and coordinated responses between Member States, especially during transnational crises. This lack of coordination leads to delays in incident response and recovery efforts, amplifying the effects of disruptions.

Supply chain vulnerabilities

The supply chain for critical infrastructure components often involves third parties that fail to meet stringent security requirements. Supply chain attacks, such as malware insertion or counterfeit components, pose a significant risk to system integrity.

Outdated physical security standards

Standards for physical security often fail to keep pace with evolving threats, such as the use of drones or hybrid attacks combining cyber and physical elements. Infrastructure remains vulnerable to physical sabotage, theft, and terrorism, which can cause cascading failures across other sectors.

Lack of comprehensive training

Current training programs are insufficient to prepare personnel for handling combined cyber-physical threats and resilience challenges. Limited skills and awareness among staff lead to slower responses and higher susceptibility to attacks.

Gaps in governance and policy implementation

Regulatory frameworks, including the CER and NIS2 directives, are not uniformly implemented, and updates often lag technological advancements. This misalignment creates inconsistencies in security measures and hinders the adoption of innovative solutions.

Absence of spatially visualised information

There is no real-time spatial visualization of critical infrastructure vulnerabilities and risks. Decision-makers and responders lack a common operational picture, leading to inefficiencies in managing crises.

Incomplete risk assessment frameworks

Existing frameworks lack comprehensive KPIs and mechanisms to assess cascading effects and long-term impacts of disruptions. This limits the ability to anticipate and mitigate risks proactively.

Challenges in data sovereignty and privacy

Ensuring data privacy and sovereignty within the proposed European Energy Data Space remains a significant challenge. Without robust mechanisms, stakeholders may be hesitant to share critical data, impeding collaboration and operational efficiency.

To address these gaps in the Energy sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Strengthen Cybersecurity Coordination:** Harmonize regulations and improve cross-border collaboration.
- **Integrate Real-Time Systems:** Deploy advanced monitoring tools that integrate cyber and physical security operations.
- **Enhance Training Programs:** Develop comprehensive training frameworks to build workforce resilience.
- **Modernize Supply Chain Security:** Implement stringent checks and certifications for third-party vendors.
- **Adopt Advanced Risk Assessments:** Introduce KPIs and cascading risk analysis tools for proactive threat management.

These recommendations align with the CER Directive and NIS2 framework, ensuring the Energy Sector is better equipped to handle the evolving threat landscape.

6.2.2. Finance Sector

The Finance Sector white paper outlines several critical gaps related to **cybersecurity, resilience, and critical infrastructure protection (CIP)**. These gaps arise from the sector's complexity, the rapid pace of technological advancements, and the evolving threat landscape. Below are the main gaps identified:

Infrastructure complexity

The coexistence of legacy systems and emerging technologies creates a complex technology stack with inherent security gaps. Some of the main impact are increases vulnerabilities in infrastructure, making it harder to implement comprehensive security measures across all systems.

Third-party risks

Financial organisations often rely on multiple technology vendors and partners, exposing sensitive data and critical assets to external risks. Weak security at a third-party level can lead to breaches and systemic failures within the financial value chain.

Limited information sharing

Despite the existence of Information Sharing and Analysis Centres (ISACs), trust issues and concerns about reputational damage hinder effective information sharing. A lack of shared threat intelligence reduces the ability to proactively address sector-wide risks.

Fragmented security measures

Security systems across the financial supply chain are often siloed, with poor interaction and integration between different systems. Increases the attack surface, making it easier for threats to exploit uncoordinated security measures.

Blockchain and crypto-asset challenges

While blockchain technology offers opportunities, it introduces unique vulnerabilities, including potential flaws in decentralized systems and third-party infrastructures. Financial organisations dealing with crypto-assets face significant challenges in maintaining secure operations.

Regulatory compliance challenges

The highly dynamic regulatory environment requires continuous updates and investments to maintain compliance with frameworks like the CER Directive and the 6th AML Directive. High costs and the need for constant adaptation strain resources, especially for smaller financial institutions.

Talent and skills gap

A pronounced lack of skilled professionals in cybersecurity and resilience planning hinders the effective implementation of security measures. This gap is exacerbated by poor credential management and weak enforcement of security protocols among employees.

Customer awareness deficiency

A significant number of customers lack cybersecurity knowledge, making them susceptible to fraud and social engineering attacks. Weak customer awareness compromises the overall security of financial services.

Evolving threats from generative AI

The emergence of tools like **FraudGPT** and **WormGPT** enables attackers to create sophisticated phishing schemes and malware. This gap increases the frequency and complexity of cyberattacks targeting financial infrastructures.

Limited use of advanced technologies

Although technologies like AI and machine learning offer potential for automating threat detection, their adoption in the finance sector remains limited. This gap increases the missed opportunities to enhance cyber-physical threat intelligence and early detection capabilities.

To address these gaps in the Finance sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Enhance collaboration:** Strengthen public-private partnerships to improve information sharing and threat intelligence.
- **Invest in advanced technologies:** Leverage AI, blockchain, and Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) to secure complex infrastructure and prevent advanced threats.
- **Address skills gaps:** Implement comprehensive training and reskilling programs for employees and customers.
- **Streamline compliance efforts:** Adopt continuous compliance processes to navigate the dynamic regulatory landscape effectively.
- **Improve threat detection:** Deploy automated tools for early detection and prevention of sophisticated attacks powered by generative AI.

These recommendations align with the EU's CIP goals and highlight the need for proactive, collaborative, and technologically advanced strategies in the finance sector.

6.2.3. Space Sector

The Space Sector white paper highlights several critical gaps that hinder effective Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in the space domain. The following gaps are analysed:

Fragmented regulatory frameworks

Regulatory schemes for ground segment operations vary significantly between countries, causing delays in the licensing and deployment of ground stations. This lack of harmonization complicates compliance and slows the development of infrastructure needed to meet the increasing demand for satellite-based services.

Funding challenges

High costs associated with building, operating, and maintaining satellite ground stations make financing difficult, especially for smaller operators. Long-term financial commitments and risks deter investment in critical space infrastructure, reducing scalability and innovation.

Vulnerabilities in satellite communication infrastructure

Challenges such as latency, bandwidth constraints, weather interference, and space debris affect the reliability of satellite communication. These limitations compromise the resilience and continuity of critical services, particularly in remote or disaster-stricken areas.

Physical and cyber threats

Ground stations, often the weakest link in satellite operations, are highly vulnerable to cyberattacks and physical sabotage. Successful attacks can compromise data integrity, disrupt operations, and lead to cascading effects across interconnected critical infrastructures.

Increasing interfaces between physical and digital assets

The convergence of physical and digital systems increases the attack surface, making integrated security management complex. Weaknesses in managing these interfaces expose infrastructure to multi-layered threats.

Fragmented security supervision systems

The market for security management systems (e.g., PSIM, SIEM) is fragmented, leading to inefficiencies in monitoring and protecting assets. A lack of standardized tools reduces the effectiveness of threat detection and incident response across space infrastructures.

Insufficient space traffic management

The increasing number of satellites and space debris has outpaced current traffic management capabilities. Risks of collisions and disruptions to critical satellite services continue to grow, threatening operational continuity.

Limited training and skills development

Training programs for managing space infrastructure risks and deploying advanced technologies are insufficient and outdated. A lack of skilled personnel hinders the effective implementation of CIP and CIR measures, slowing the adoption of innovative solutions.

To address these gaps in the Space sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Harmonize Regulatory Frameworks:** Advocate for international standardization of licensing and compliance processes to streamline infrastructure development.
- **Enhance Funding Mechanisms:** Explore public-private partnerships and alternative financing models to reduce the financial burden on small operators.
- **Adopt Advanced Security Measures:** Deploy holistic frameworks integrating cybersecurity, physical security, and AI-driven threat detection tools.
- **Develop Space Traffic Management Systems:** Implement advanced systems for debris monitoring and collision avoidance using AI and enhanced sensors.
- **Invest in Workforce Development:** Create comprehensive training programs emphasizing real-world scenarios, risk management, and continuous learning.
- **Promote Collaborative Research:** Foster cross-sectoral and international partnerships to address complex challenges and drive innovation.

These gaps and recommendations emphasize the need for proactive measures to enhance the resilience, security, and sustainability of critical space infrastructures.

6.2.4. Telecommunications Sector

The telecommunications sector white paper outlines significant gaps in the protection of critical infrastructure, emphasising challenges posed by evolving threats, technological complexity, and operational vulnerabilities:

Insufficient situational awareness

Ineffective dynamic risk modelling and lack of visibility over cascading effects of hybrid threats. Limited ability to anticipate or respond to interconnected risks across telecom infrastructure, such as disruptions in data centres, fibre-optic networks, and wireless systems.

Complex and vulnerable infrastructure

Migration across generations of networks (e.g., 4G to 5G and beyond) increases complexity, exposing vulnerabilities in legacy systems, cloud-based services, and IoT deployments. This situation creates a wide attack surface for cyber and physical threats, complicating infrastructure management for operators and subcontractors.

Gaps in supply chain security

Heavy reliance on third-party vendors for hardware, software, and managed services introduces vulnerabilities throughout the supply chain. Supply chain disruptions, such as the exploitation of Operational Technology (OT) networks, can propagate risks into the broader infrastructure, as demonstrated by incidents like the SolarWinds breach.

Limited collaboration and threat intelligence sharing

Operators lack robust frameworks for sharing threat intelligence with industry peers, government agencies, and academia. This reduces the sector's ability to detect and respond to emerging threats targeting interconnected systems.

Outdated exposure management processes

Absence of cohesive exposure management processes to handle the vast attack surface introduced by multi-generational network elements and endpoints. This gap increases vulnerability to attacks targeting under-monitored or misconfigured elements within the infrastructure.

Insufficient focus on hybrid threats

Limited integration of strategies to address hybrid threats, combining cyber and physical attacks targeting telecom infrastructure. This situation opens gaps in securing critical sites like communication cables, data centres, and satellite systems.

Talent and skills gaps

Challenges in attracting and retaining skilled cybersecurity professionals capable of managing complex telecom systems. This gap increases reliance on subcontractors and creates operational bottlenecks, particularly during crisis scenarios.

Regulatory and policy challenges

Misalignment between innovation-driven policies (e.g., 5G deployment) and security regulations. This gap hinders the adoption of cohesive security measures while balancing cost and compliance pressures.

To address these gaps in the Telecommunications sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Enhance Situational Awareness:** Implement dynamic risk modelling tools that assess cascading effects and provide real-time insights into hybrid threats.
- **Strengthen Supply Chain Security:** Adopt Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA) for vendor integrations and conduct regular audits of third-party systems.

- **Foster Collaboration:** Develop public-private-academic partnerships for collaborative intelligence sharing and response planning.
- **Modernise Exposure Management:** Introduce automated exposure management processes to reduce vulnerabilities across multi-generational network components.
- **Invest in Workforce Development:** Create targeted training programs to upskill professionals in cybersecurity and operational technology management.
- **Address Hybrid Threats:** Integrate cyber-physical security frameworks to protect critical sites like data centres and satellite networks.
- **Align Policies with Security Needs:** Advocate for regulatory frameworks that balance innovation, affordability, and comprehensive security measures.

These gaps reflect the urgent need for coordinated action to enhance resilience, streamline operations, and ensure the integrity of telecommunications infrastructure in the face of evolving threats.

6.2.5. Transport Sector

The Transport Sector white paper outlines key challenges and gaps that hinder the resilience and protection of critical infrastructure. These gaps are categorised into the following areas:

Cybersecurity deficits

The sector faces a growing threat from cyberattacks, including ransomware, APTs, DoS attacks, and supply chain attacks. A lack of robust cybersecurity frameworks leaves critical systems (e.g., ticketing systems, traffic control) vulnerable to significant disruptions.

Dependency on GNSS

Transport systems heavily rely on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) for navigation, logistics, and operations. Disruptions to GNSS services can lead to widespread operational failures, affecting port operations, railways, and air traffic systems.

Vulnerability to hybrid threats

The transport sector is increasingly exposed to hybrid threats, including cyber-physical attacks targeting both digital and physical infrastructures. Insufficient integration of cyber and physical security measures results in uncoordinated responses to complex threats.

Lack of climate resilience

Extreme weather events, such as flooding, hurricanes, and wildfires, exacerbate the vulnerabilities of transport infrastructure. Aging infrastructure and limited investments in climate adaptation measures increase the frequency and severity of disruptions.

Supply chain risks

The transport sector's interdependence on complex supply chains makes it susceptible to supply chain attacks. Compromised suppliers or service providers can disrupt operations across multiple nodes in the transport network.

Workforce challenges

An aging workforce combined with a shortage of skilled professionals hampers the sector's ability to implement and maintain CIP and CIR measures. Operational inefficiencies and delays in addressing emerging threats are exacerbated by this skills gap.

Physical security weaknesses

Insufficient measures to prevent physical attacks, such as terrorism or insider threats, on critical transport infrastructure. Damage to transport hubs, bridges, and rail systems can cause cascading disruptions across other critical sectors.

Aging infrastructure

Many roads, bridges, and railways are nearing the end of their lifecycle, requiring extensive repair or replacement. This reduces the reliability and safety of transport systems while increasing maintenance costs.

Limited cross-sectoral integration

The transport sector's interdependencies with Energy, Telecommunications, and Space sectors are not adequately addressed. Cascading failures across interconnected sectors amplify risks, particularly during large-scale disruptions.

To address these gaps in the Transport sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Enhance Cybersecurity Frameworks:** Implement advanced threat detection and response tools to counteract ransomware, APTs, and supply chain attacks.
- **Improve Climate Resilience:** Invest in climate-adaptive designs and predictive tools to mitigate the impact of extreme weather events.
- **Strengthen GNSS Backup Systems:** Develop alternative navigation systems to reduce reliance on GNSS.
- **Integrate Cyber-Physical Security:** Adopt unified frameworks to address hybrid threats comprehensively.
- **Upskill the Workforce:** Provide targeted training programs for cybersecurity and critical infrastructure management.
- **Modernise Infrastructure:** Allocate funding to repair and replace aging transport systems, incorporating resilience into designs.
- **Foster Cross-Sector Collaboration:** Establish coordination mechanisms with Energy, Telecommunications, and Space sectors to manage cascading risks effectively.

These gaps highlight the urgent need for coordinated and innovative approaches to safeguard the transport sector against evolving challenges.

6.2.6. Water Sector

The Water Sector white paper identifies several critical gaps impacting the resilience and security of water infrastructure. These gaps highlight challenges related to digital transformation, integrated security, and workforce preparedness.

Limited integration between cyber and physical security

Cyber and physical security are managed separately, leading to fragmented defence mechanisms. Water systems are increasingly vulnerable to cyber-physical attacks that exploit the interdependencies between digital and physical components, such as contamination or service disruption.

Lack of situational awareness

There is a significant gap in collective situational awareness regarding cyber threats. Water utilities and IT providers do not systematically share information about incidents, hindering the sector's ability to assess risks and improve preparedness.

Immature cybersecurity culture

A lack of cybersecurity awareness and training across the sector limits the effectiveness of prevention and response strategies. Approximately 90% of cyberattacks are attributed to human error, and limited competence creates barriers to digital transformation.

Supply chain risks

Risks related to integrating digital solutions into water utilities are not sufficiently addressed, particularly in supply chain contexts. A focus on rapid market entry often prioritizes functionality over security, increasing the likelihood of supply chain attacks.

Challenges in digital transformation

The slower adoption of digital solutions in the water sector is influenced by concerns over security risks and insufficient investment. This hinders the implementation of advanced technologies, such as IoT and real-time monitoring systems, to enhance resilience.

Fragmented information sharing

Operators lack structured frameworks for sharing best practices and threat intelligence, both within the water sector and across critical infrastructure sectors. This fragmentation reduces the ability to coordinate responses to emerging threats effectively.

Training deficits

There is insufficient training for operators and decision-makers in cybersecurity and integrated risk management. The sector lacks the capacity to respond effectively to cascading risks from combined cyber-physical threats.

Underutilisation of advanced risk management approaches

Proven tools and methods, such as stress-testing platforms and integrated cyber-physical risk management solutions, are not widely adopted. This limits the ability of water utilities to anticipate, mitigate, and respond to risks comprehensively.

Lack of EU-wide collaboration

The absence of a centralized platform, such as a Water ISAC (Information Sharing and Analysis Centre), hinders collective situational awareness and sector-wide collaboration. Individual operators are left to manage cybersecurity risks in isolation, reducing overall sectoral resilience.

To address these gaps in the Water sector, the following **recommendations** should be followed:

- **Integrate Cyber and Physical Security:** Develop a unified approach to risk management that addresses both cyber and physical vulnerabilities as part of an integrated security framework.

- **Enhance Threat Awareness:** Establish mechanisms for real-time information sharing, including an EU Water ISAC, to foster collaboration and improve situational awareness.
- **Promote Training and Awareness:** Implement EU-wide training programs focusing on cybersecurity, digital transformation, and incident response.
- **Strengthen Supply Chain Security:** Provide guidelines for securely integrating digital solutions and ensure compliance with standards such as the NIS2 Directive.
- **Accelerate Digital Transformation:** Invest in IoT, real-time monitoring, and AI-driven analytics to improve operational efficiency and resilience.
- **Adopt Advanced Risk Management Tools:** Utilise stress-testing platforms and scenario-based exercises to prepare for cascading risks and hybrid threats.

These gaps and recommendations underscore the importance of addressing structural vulnerabilities, fostering collaboration, and advancing digital transformation to enhance the resilience of water infrastructure.

The analysis of gaps across all critical infrastructure sectors (Water, Energy, Finance, Space, Telecommunications, and Transport) reveals pervasive vulnerabilities and challenges that hinder resilience and protection efforts. These include fragmented cybersecurity measures, insufficient integration of cyber-physical security frameworks, and a lack of real-time situational awareness, which leave sectors exposed to hybrid threats and cascading failures. Issues like aging infrastructure, supply chain vulnerabilities, and inadequate workforce training further exacerbate risks. The importance of this gap analysis lies in its ability to pinpoint these systemic weaknesses and guide the development of targeted recommendations and guidelines. Addressing these gaps requires a coordinated, cross-sectoral approach that prioritizes unified security strategies, collaborative threat intelligence sharing, regulatory alignment with EU directives like CER and NIS2, and the adoption of advanced technologies such as IoT, AI, and digital twins. By leveraging these insights, sectors can enhance their resilience and ensure the continuity of essential services in an increasingly complex threat landscape.

6.3. Notable changes in the CIP/CIR Technological, Innovation, and Policy Landscape

The analysis of the main changes in technological, innovation, and policy domains provides a comprehensive view of how sectors are adapting to ensure long-term sustainability, security, and resilience in the face of an increasingly complex threat environment.

6.3.1. Water Sector

- **Cyber-physical convergence:** Increased integration of physical and cyber infrastructures highlights vulnerabilities to sophisticated cyber-physical attacks. The adoption of IoT and IT-centric control systems amplifies exposure to cybersecurity threats.
- **Defence-in-depth strategies:** Emphasis on holistic approaches to interdependencies among vulnerabilities, threats, and mitigation measures.

- **Policy developments:** Calls for an EU-wide Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (ISAC) to enhance situational awareness and collaboration.

6.3.2. Energy Sector

- **Regulatory advances:** Introduction of the CER Directive and NIS2 to enhance resilience against hybrid threats and cascading effects.
- **Technological innovations:** Deployment of digital twins, AI, and real-time monitoring systems to bolster operational insights and resilience.
- **Threat landscape:** Increasing cyberattacks on OT systems, leveraging vulnerabilities in industrial protocols.

6.3.3. Finance Sector

- **Digital transformation:** Accelerated adoption of AI, blockchain, and mobile banking solutions, introducing new vulnerabilities.
- **Regulatory developments:** Implementation of the CER Directive and AML rules to strengthen financial security.
- **Emerging risks:** Use of generative AI tools like FraudGPT for sophisticated attacks.

6.3.4. Space Sector

- **Infrastructure expansion:** Growth in Earth Observation (EO) and satellite communication infrastructure driven by high-throughput satellites and mega-constellations.
- **Security needs:** Increased risks to satellite data confidentiality and operational continuity from hybrid threats.
- **Policy and regulation:** Need for harmonized licensing frameworks for ground stations to streamline global operations.

6.3.5. Telecommunications Sector

- **Hybrid threats:** Escalation of hybrid attacks targeting interconnected networks, including 5G, IoT, and data centres.
- **Fragmented visibility:** Challenges in managing exposure across legacy and modern network components.
- **Collaborative efforts:** Importance of public-private partnerships for threat intelligence sharing.

6.3.6. Transport Sector

- **Reliance on space and digital systems:** Dependence on GNSS and electrified infrastructure increases risks from cyber-physical threats.
- **Climate change:** Heightened vulnerability to extreme weather events, necessitating climate-resilient designs.
- **Cross-sector interdependencies:** Risks of cascading failures due to interconnected infrastructures.

6.3.7. Cross-Sectorial Changes

The white papers reveal several key cross-sectorial changes that are shaping the landscape of **CIP and CIR**. These changes reflect the evolving threat environment, technological advancements, and regulatory transformations impacting all sectors:

Hybrid threat escalation

Increased frequency and sophistication of hybrid threats combining cyber and physical elements. Sectors like Energy, Transport, and Telecommunications report growing vulnerabilities to ransomware, APTs, and sabotage targeting interconnected systems. Attacks leveraging generative AI (e.g., FraudGPT) and malware like Industroyer2 highlight the need for advanced defence mechanisms. A potential response consists in cross-sector adoption of integrated security frameworks that address cyber-physical interdependencies.

Data-driven resilience

Greater reliance on real-time data analytics and digital twins for monitoring and decision-making. Energy and Water sectors are leveraging IoT and AI-powered analytics to predict disruptions and optimize maintenance. Space and Telecommunications sectors emphasise the importance of secure data exchange platforms like the European Energy Data Space. Sectors must implement privacy-preserving technologies (e.g., Trusted Execution Environments) and scalable data-sharing mechanisms to enhance resilience.

Climate adaptation

Climate change is emerging as a critical driver of infrastructure risk, with extreme weather events posing significant threats. Transport and Water sectors face increased physical risks, requiring climate-resilient infrastructure designs. Space sector highlights the role of Earth Observation (EO) for real-time climate monitoring and risk mitigation. Adoption of climate-adaptive technologies and predictive tools across all sectors helps to anticipate and mitigate impacts.

Policy harmonization and implementation

New EU directives like CER and NIS2 aim to create a unified framework for CIP and CIR. Regulatory alignment is crucial for sectors such as Finance, Telecommunications, and Energy, but implementation challenges persist across Member States. Lack of standardized metrics and compliance monitoring hinders uniform adoption. Establishment of governance bodies like the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC) to coordinate regulatory enforcement and best practices could mitigate this situation.

Technological convergence

Increasing integration of emerging technologies like blockchain, AI, and 5G across sectors. Finance and Space sectors lead in leveraging blockchain for secure transactions and data integrity. Energy and Telecommunications sectors benefit from AI for real-time monitoring and anomaly detection but face challenges in scaling these solutions securely. Cross-sector investments in R&D and pilot projects can ensure the safe deployment of converging technologies.

Evolving role of collaboration

Greater emphasis on public-private partnerships and cross-sector intelligence sharing. Sectors recognise the importance of collaborative models like ISACs (Information Sharing and Analysis Centres) to enhance situational awareness and coordinate responses. Transport and Telecommunications sectors highlight the need for shared threat intelligence platforms to counter cascading risks. Development of secure, interoperable collaboration tools facilitate real-time threat communication.

Addressing supply chain risks

Growing awareness of vulnerabilities in third-party components and service providers. Supply chain attacks, such as compromised OT and software dependencies, impact Energy, Water, and Telecommunications sectors. Space sector faces challenges in securing satellite manufacturing and ground segment operations. A potential response consists in the implementation of Zero Trust Architecture and vendor compliance audits across all critical sectors.

Focus on workforce development

Sectors face a shortage of skilled professionals to manage complex security and resilience challenges. Energy and Finance sectors report significant gaps in cybersecurity expertise. Limited training programs hinder preparedness for emerging threats, particularly in hybrid scenarios. Establishment of EU-wide training initiatives and simulation-based exercises tailored to sector-specific needs could enhance this situation.

Increasing importance of interdependencies

Recognition of cascading risks from interconnected critical infrastructures. Energy failures impact Telecommunications, while GNSS disruptions in Transport have ripple effects on Logistics and Finance. Water and Space sectors highlight the critical need for cross-sector contingency planning. A potential response consists in the adoption of cross-sectoral risk assessment frameworks and shared resilience metrics to manage cascading impacts effectively.

Innovation-driven transformation

Accelerated adoption of advanced tools like AI, digital twins, and Earth Observation technologies. Space and Energy sectors are pioneers in integrating digital twins for operational optimization. Transport and Water sectors are slower to adopt innovative solutions due to resource constraints and regulatory barriers. Increased funding for innovation and policy incentives can drive adoption in underperforming sectors.

These cross-sectorial changes reflect a rapidly evolving CIP/CIR landscape, where hybrid threats, technological innovation, and regulatory alignment are reshaping resilience strategies. Addressing these trends requires collaborative, data-driven, and forward-looking approaches that integrate cutting-edge technologies, harmonized policies, and cross-sectoral intelligence sharing.

6.4. Technological, Scientific, and Research Megatrends in CIP/CIR

From the sectoral white papers, the following megatrends emerge, highlighting technological, scientific, and research advancements shaping the CIP/CIR landscape:

1. Data-driven innovation and digitalization

- **Energy and finance sectors:**

- Increasing deployment of **IoT**, **Edge Computing**, and **Cloud Platforms** as part of the "Computing Continuum" to optimize operations and resilience.
- Growth in the use of **Digital Twins** and advanced analytics for real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance.
- In finance, **AI-driven fraud detection** and risk assessments are transforming cybersecurity and operational transparency.

- **Space sector:**

- Expansion in the use of **Earth Observation (EO)** data to enhance situational awareness and environmental monitoring.

2. Hybrid threat landscape

- **Telecommunications and energy sectors:**

- Growing hybrid threats that combine **cyber-physical attacks**, targeting multi-layered infrastructures like 5G networks, Operational Technology (OT), and renewable energy grids.
- Emergence of AI-powered attack tools (e.g., **FraudGPT**) creating sophisticated new risks.

3. Policy and regulatory advances

- Across all sectors, the adoption of the **Critical Entities Resilience (CER)** and **NIS2** directives is harmonizing EU-wide resilience and cybersecurity practices.
- In the financial sector, regulatory innovations are being introduced to manage **crypto-assets** and digital currencies.

4. Collaborative research and innovation

- Enhanced focus on cross-sector **Research and Innovation (R&I)** fosters partnerships for shared threat intelligence and the deployment of advanced technologies.
- The space sector emphasizes collaborations to advance satellite communication capabilities, enabling rapid innovation cycles.

5. Climate adaptation and sustainability

- **Water and transport sectors:**

- Integration of **climate-resilient designs** to address vulnerabilities caused by extreme weather events.

- **Space and energy sectors:**
 - Utilization of **Earth Observation (EO)** and renewable technologies for environmental monitoring and climate adaptation.

6. Privacy-preserving technologies

- **Energy and finance sectors:**
 - Development of secure **data exchange frameworks** using privacy-preserving mechanisms like **Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)** and advanced encryption.

7. Emerging infrastructure models

- **Space sector:**
 - Transition towards **Ground Station-as-a-Service (GSaaS)**, driven by agile NewSpace entrants and major technology players like Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Microsoft.
- **Telecommunications sector:**
 - Adoption of virtualization and **high-throughput satellite systems** to enhance data transmission capacities.

8. Talent and skills development

- Cross-sector challenges include upskilling the workforce in cybersecurity, hybrid threat management, and advanced operational technologies to bridge the skills gap.

These trends reflect a transformative shift towards advanced digital ecosystems, collaborative innovation, and regulatory alignment, offering robust pathways for enhancing CIP/CIR across all critical sectors.

6.5. Future evolution of policies, standards, technologies, and research results

The white papers across critical infrastructure sectors emphasise the evolving landscape of policies, standards, technologies, and research efforts, highlighting a more interconnected, secure, and resilient approach to CIP and CIR. Key consolidated ideas include:

1. Policies and regulations

- **Strengthening EU frameworks:**
 - Directives such as CER (Critical Entities Resilience) and NIS2 aim to harmonize regulations across Member States, focusing on strengthening resilience against hybrid threats.
 - Policies targeting specific sectors, such as the European Data Spaces initiative for energy and cybersecurity mandates for telecommunications, underline the importance of domain-specific regulations.

- **Global cooperation:**

- Collaborative international frameworks and standards for sectors like space emphasize harmonized protocols and enhanced information sharing to address global risks.

2. Standardisation and best practices

- **Unified standards:**

- Adoption of international standards such as IEC 62443 (industrial control systems) and ECSS standards (space sector) ensures seamless interoperability across infrastructures.
- A focus on updating and maintaining dynamic standards is essential to address evolving technological and threat landscapes.

3. Advancing technology integration

- **Emerging technologies:**

- Integration of **IoT**, **AI**, and **digital twins** enables real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and hybrid threat detection, transforming resilience strategies in sectors like energy, water, and telecommunications.
- Quantum technologies, including encryption and communication, promise revolutionary advancements in securing sensitive data in critical sectors such as space.

- **Data-driven strategies:**

- Adoption of advanced data-sharing ecosystems, such as the European Energy Data Space, reflects the move towards collaborative data management and privacy-preserving frameworks.

4. Research and innovation (R&I)

- **Collaborative R&D:**

- Cross-sector R&I initiatives prioritize solutions for critical challenges, such as integrating cybersecurity into legacy systems and developing climate-resilient infrastructure.
- Space and telecommunications sectors emphasize academic-industry partnerships to foster innovation ecosystems and public-private collaborations.

- **Impact assessment:**

- Introduction of monitoring frameworks ensures the evaluation of R&I activities in enhancing sectoral security and resilience.

5. Addressing workforce gaps

- **Reskilling and upskilling:**

- Training programs focused on advanced technologies, cybersecurity, and resilience planning are critical to closing skills gaps and enhancing operational readiness across sectors.

- **Knowledge exchange:**

- Promoting international and cross-sector knowledge sharing through forums, seminars, and collaborative platforms ensures the dissemination of best practices and innovations.

These consolidated ideas underline a transformative approach to CIP and CIR, where harmonized policies, cutting-edge technologies, and robust R&I ecosystems converge to address contemporary challenges. This framework fosters collaboration and innovation, ensuring the sustainability and security of critical infrastructures across all sectors.

6.6. Foresight in CIP/CIR landscape

The white papers collectively offer valuable foresight regarding the evolution of CIP/CIR across sectors. The insights emphasise integrated, technology-driven, and collaborative approaches to address emerging threats and enhance infrastructure resilience. Key highlights include:

1. Technological integration

- **Emerging technologies:**

- Deployment of **IoT, AI, digital twins**, and **edge computing** as essential tools for predictive analytics, real-time monitoring, and operational optimization in sectors such as Energy, Transport, and Water.
- Use of advanced encryption and **quantum technologies** in the Space and Finance sectors to secure sensitive data and communications.

- **Data Management:**

- The creation of **secure European Data Spaces** in Energy and Telecommunications sectors highlights the importance of privacy-preserving and interoperable data-sharing frameworks.

2. Policy evolution

- **Regulatory enhancements:**

- Implementation of the **CER and NIS2 Directives** as unified frameworks to strengthen infrastructure resilience against hybrid threats.
- Sector-specific regulations for cryptocurrency and digital finance in the Finance sector, aligned with the broader EU Digital Finance Strategy.

- **Global standards:**

- Growing adherence to international standards, such as IEC 62443 for industrial cybersecurity and ECSS for space operations, ensures global alignment.

3. Resilience and Risk management

- **Cross-Sector dependencies:**

- Increased interconnectivity among critical infrastructures calls for **hybrid situation awareness** systems that integrate cyber and physical threat intelligence.

- **Climate resilience:**

- Adoption of climate-resilient designs in Transport and Water sectors to mitigate risks from extreme weather and natural disasters.

4. Research and collaboration

- **Collaborative R&I:**

- Emphasis on EU-wide collaborative R&I projects to address legacy system vulnerabilities and foster innovation.
- Strengthened academic-industry partnerships across sectors to accelerate technology transfer and deployment.

- **Knowledge exchange:**

- Promotion of regular cross-sector knowledge-sharing programs and public-private collaborations to align resilience strategies and share best practices.

5. Operational and workforce trends

- **Workforce development:**

- Expansion of training programs to address skills gaps in cybersecurity, resilience planning, and hybrid threat management across all sectors.

- **Operational transformation:**

- Digital transformation in sectors like Finance and Telecommunications is redefining resilience strategies, focusing on hybrid operational models.

These foresights demonstrate a systemic shift towards resilience by integrating advanced technologies, harmonized policies, and collaborative research. They provide a roadmap for sectors to adapt proactively to evolving threats and regulatory changes, ensuring long-term sustainability and security of critical infrastructures.

7. Recommendations for Improving the Regulatory, Standards and Ethical Landscape

The evolving landscape of critical infrastructure protection necessitates a robust framework for regulatory, standards, and ethical considerations. As technological advancements continue to reshape the operational paradigms of critical infrastructures, it is imperative to establish comprehensive recommendations that address the regulatory challenges, promote innovation, and ensure ethical compliance. This section outlines key recommendations focused on research and development actions, technology development actions, and policy actions that can enhance the resilience and security of critical infrastructures across Europe.

7.1. R&D Actions

R&D actions are fundamental to advancing the capabilities of critical infrastructure systems, particularly in the context of emerging threats and technological advancements. To cultivate innovation, it is imperative to *prioritize funding for R&D initiatives* that delve into *transformative technologies such as AI, machine learning, and advanced data analytics*. These technologies possess the potential to significantly enhance predictive maintenance, real-time monitoring, and data-driven decision-making processes within critical infrastructures. By harnessing these capabilities, stakeholders can proactively address vulnerabilities and improve operational efficiency.

Moreover, *establishing dedicated research programs* aimed at identifying and mitigating vulnerabilities within critical infrastructures is essential. These programs should focus on developing innovative solutions that bolster resilience against a spectrum of threats, including cyberattacks, natural disasters, and other disruptions. For instance, the **Horizon Europe** program provides a robust framework for funding collaborative R&D projects that engage academia, industry stakeholders, and government agencies. Such collaborations leverage diverse expertise and resources, fostering a multidisciplinary approach to problem-solving. By promoting a culture of continuous improvement through R&D, stakeholders can ensure that critical infrastructure systems remain adaptive and responsive to evolving challenges.

In addition to fostering innovation, there is a pressing need for *research initiatives that assess the effectiveness of resilience measures implemented across various sectors*. Developing standardised metrics for evaluating the impact of new technologies on operational efficiency and security will enable stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding future investments. The insights gained from these evaluations can guide the refinement of existing technologies and inform the development of new solutions tailored to the unique challenges faced by critical infrastructure sectors.

7.2. Technology Development Actions

Technology development actions are crucial for translating research findings into practical applications that enhance the resilience of critical infrastructures. A key recommendation is to *promote the adoption of standardised technologies* across different sectors of critical infrastructure. Standardisation not only facilitates interoperability among systems but also ensures that best practices are consistently applied in the deployment of new technologies. The **European**

Committee for Standardization (CEN) plays a vital role in this regard by developing standards that address safety, security, and performance criteria relevant to critical infrastructure.

Investment in pilot projects that test innovative solutions in real-world scenarios is also paramount. These pilot programs provide invaluable insights into the effectiveness of new technologies while identifying potential challenges prior to widespread implementation. Engaging stakeholders from various sectors in these pilot initiatives fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing, ultimately leading to more resilient infrastructure systems. The **Digital Europe Programme** emphasizes the importance of such pilot initiatives as part of its strategy to support the deployment of cutting-edge technologies across Europe.

Furthermore, establishing comprehensive frameworks for evaluating technology performance in enhancing resilience is essential. Metrics should be developed to assess the impact of new technologies on operational efficiency, security, and overall resilience of critical infrastructures. By systematically evaluating technology performance through established benchmarks, stakeholders can make informed decisions regarding future investments and improvements. This approach not only enhances accountability but also ensures that technological advancements align with broader strategic objectives for critical infrastructure protection.

7.3. Policy Actions

Effective policy actions are necessary to create an enabling environment for innovation in critical infrastructure protection. Policymakers should focus on developing comprehensive regulatory frameworks that align with technological advancements while addressing ethical considerations inherent in emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things. Revising existing regulations to accommodate these innovations while ensuring compliance with data protection laws is crucial for fostering public trust and promoting responsible development.

Engaging stakeholders in the policymaking process is essential for crafting relevant and effective policies. Regular consultations with industry leaders, researchers, and civil society organizations can yield valuable insights into the challenges faced by critical infrastructure sectors and help shape policies that promote resilience and security. The **Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive**, introduced by the European Commission, serves as a foundational policy framework aimed at enhancing the resilience of entities providing essential services across Europe.

Moreover, fostering international cooperation on regulatory standards is imperative in an increasingly interconnected world. Collaborative efforts among EU member states can lead to harmonized regulations that facilitate cross-border operations while enhancing overall security measures across critical infrastructures. The establishment of platforms for dialogue among member states can promote best practices and encourage a unified approach to addressing common challenges in critical infrastructure protection.

Implementing these recommendations for improving the regulatory, standards, and ethical landscape will significantly contribute to enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructures throughout Europe. By prioritizing R&D actions, promoting technology development initiatives, and establishing effective policy frameworks aligned with EU directives like the CER Directive, stakeholders can ensure that critical infrastructures are well-equipped to face current and future challenges.

8. Conclusions and Future Outlook

This report represents another important milestone in the EU-CIP project's ongoing effort to identify capability gaps in Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR), assess technological developments to address these gaps, and provide actionable roadmaps to guide the development, validation, commercialization, and adoption of essential solutions.

Building on the analyses and findings of v2 and v3, this edition deepens the examination of technological outcomes, stakeholder perspectives, and regulatory frameworks. It highlights several persistent and emerging gaps that must be addressed to enhance the security and resilience of critical services across sectors such as energy, transport, finance, telecommunications, and water.

A key advancement in this report is the integration of insights from three targeted surveys conducted with members of the EU-CIP knowledge network. These surveys confirm and reinforce earlier findings on technological gaps and highlight priority actions, including enhanced stakeholder collaboration, regulatory alignment, the development and integration of new technologies, and targeted training and reskilling.

The sectoral analysis has also been expanded through a series of focused white papers covering energy, transport, water, finance, telecommunications, and space. These open-access documents, available via the EU-CIP Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-cip/>), offer in-depth, sector-specific insights and recommendations with an outlook toward 2030. Future editions will extend this coverage to additional sectors, such as maritime.

This report also provides an initial assessment of how technologies like artificial intelligence can support compliance with new directives such as CER, while outlining related deployment challenges. Updates on research, policy, and technological developments are included, and the annex offers further detail on the projects analyzed and supporting evidence for the main findings.

Looking ahead, the next edition (v5) will build on these insights to deliver an updated map of opportunities and constraints for the exploitation of EU security research and innovation projects. There will be a particular focus on industrialization, commercialization, adoption, and deployment of innovative solutions to address common capability gaps. This iterative approach will continue to refine and enhance the strategic roadmaps, ensuring they are informed by the latest technological advances, stakeholder feedback, and regulatory developments.

By regularly updating and expanding this analysis, the EU-CIP project remains committed to empowering stakeholders with the knowledge, tools, and strategies needed to strengthen the resilience and security of Europe's critical infrastructures.

Acknowledgement:

The main EU projects contributing with data to the surveys of EU-CIP were:

<https://cybersecdome.eu/>

<https://harpocrates-project.eu/>

<https://r2d2project.eu>

<https://energy-shield.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

<https://sunrise-europe.eu/>

<https://efort-project.eu/>

INTACT - Integrated software toolbox for secure IoT-Cloud computing (2 RESPONSES)

<https://nemecys.eu/>

<https://ai4cyber.eu/>

<https://praetorian-h2020.eu/>

<https://dynabic.eu/>

<https://www.atlantis-horizon.eu/>

<https://satie-h2020.eu>

<https://www.impetus-project.eu/>

<https://www.securegas-project.eu/>

www.eucip.eu/

<https://www.ensuresec.eu/>

[STOP-IT » project about protection of critical water infrastructures](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

9. Annex A: Historical overview of security research projects

9.1. Annex A.1: EU projects linked to CIR/CIP

The following overview lists EU projects related to CIR/CIP, identified by Open Call A winners Ilias Gkotsis and Lennart Walter Landsberg (Table 2 and following sections). Projects already included in the survey analysed (“Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience: Outcomes, Future Trends, Lessons Learned, and Best Practices from Past and Current Security Research Projects”) are marked in *italics*. The remaining projects have not yet been covered and will be included in further data collection and analysis as part of the EU-CIP project surveys.

Table 2: Overview lists EU projects related to CIR/CIP

Project Name	Key Elements	Objectives	Connection to EU-CIP
SAFEguard of Critical heAlth infrastructure (SAFECARE)	- Physical security systems (e.g., SBDS, IFDS)	Enhance cyber and physical security in healthcare infrastructures	Ensures the protection of healthcare critical infrastructure at national and EU levels
	- Cybersecurity systems (e.g., ITTDS, EDSA)		
	- Integrated solutions (e.g., DXL, CDB)		
Securing The European Gas Network (SecureGas)	- Safety and Security platform	Secure the EU gas network from cyber-physical threats	Addresses integrity and security of gas networks in compliance with EU regulations
	- Cyber-physical correlator	Provide methodologies and tools for resilience	
	- Blockchain for data integrity		
Project NOWATER	- Risk management strategies	Increase resilience of hospitals regarding water supply	Links water supply resilience to the overall functionality of healthcare facilities
	- Emergency preparedness planning	Protect public health during crises	
	- Practical solutions for water supply		
Project Impress	- Core taxonomy and semantic reference model	Improve health services preparedness and response	Enhances the resilience of health services, essential for crisis management
	- Integrated multi-agency coordination		
Project S-HELP	- Research and analysis phases	Develop a holistic approach for healthcare preparedness and response	Aims for increased resilience in health sectors during emergencies
	- Training and evaluation components		
Project SNOWBALL	- Cascading effects analysis	- Enhance EU preparedness for large crises	Addresses the anticipation of cascading effects affecting multiple CIs
	- Decision Support System for crisis monitoring		
Project STOP-IT	- <i>All-hazards risk management framework</i>	<i>Protect critical water infrastructures from cyber-physical threats</i>	<i>Focuses on securing essential water services as critical infrastructure</i>
	- <i>Modular solutions for water infrastructure</i>		

Project DRIVER+	- Crisis management test-bed	Innovate crisis management across Europe	Improves crisis management capabilities for sustaining CIs
	- Portfolio of Crisis Management Solutions		
Project ATLANTIS	- Cross-border pilots in transport, energy, health	Improve resilience and knowledge of systemic risks	Enhances security measures for interconnected CIs across Europe
Project LINKS	- Study of disaster governance	Bridge technology and society for disaster resilience	Enhances coordination among public authorities and community response
	- Strengthening community resilience		
Project MEDiate	- Decision-support for multi-hazard risk management	Develop a framework for effective disaster risk assessment	Helps policymakers assess risk management strategies for community resilience
Project RESILOC	- Community resilience assessment tools	Increase resilience understanding and innovation	Focuses on local community risk preparedness and management
	- Local Resilience Teams		
Project ENGAGE	- Analysis of past disasters and citizen support	Improve community skills in disaster response	Enhances local community engagement in crisis management
Project BUILDERS	- Understanding risks among vulnerable populations	Strengthen social capital and preparedness	Addresses vulnerabilities within CI communities
Project KIRMin	- Interdependencies in critical infrastructure	Minimum supply concept during crises	Supports the understanding of interdependencies in CI resilience
Project PRAETORIAN	- Tool-set for cyber-physical threat analysis	Secure CIs against combined threats	Develops tools specific to CI stakeholder needs
Project SMARTResilience	- Resilience indicator identification	Improve resiliency against threats	Focuses on advancing smart infrastructure resilience
	- Interactive dashboard tool		
Project INFRARISK	- Stress testing for natural hazard impacts	Create a comprehensive hazard assessment method	Supports EU-CIP by identifying risks to critical infrastructures

SAFeguard of Critical heAlth infrastructure (SAFECARE) - GA 787002

The main aim of the SAFECARE project is to foster the creation of solutions for the improvement of cyber and physical security in the healthcare context, with specific regard to healthcare infrastructures. The SAFECARE global architecture can be broken down into 3 parts, Physical security solutions, Cyber security solutions, Integrated cyber-physical security solutions, each of which is composed of several dedicated systems:

The physical security solutions rely on:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

- The suspicious behaviour detection system (SBDS), based on machine learning models over video surveillance cameras.
- The intrusion and fire detection system (IFDS), fusing data from multiple sources (Video Management System, Access Management System, Fire Detection System)
- The data collection system (DCS), sends fire detection events to the intrusion and fire detection system, and also sends security events to the building threat monitoring system.
- The mobile alerting system (MAS), functions as an information exchange channel between the local security agents and health personnel inside the hospital and the security modules.
- And the building threat monitoring system (BTMS), which is the central point for communicating incidents, also responsible for receiving and relaying the incident handling response and decision support, providing a graphical user interface.

The cyber security solutions rely on:

- The IT threat detection system (ITTDS) is capable of detecting known cyber-attacks as well as suspicious behaviours that may be the work of a new unknown method for an attacker to slip into or harm the system.
- The BMS threat detection system (BTDS), a network intrusion detection system focused on Operational Technology (OT), including protocols used in industrial control systems and building automation systems.
- The advanced file analysis system (AFAS), capable of detecting malicious files in critical health infrastructures by performing an in-depth analysis - both statically and dynamically - of files that transit through the IT and BMS networks.
- The e-health devices security analytics (EDSA), offers security analytics and monitoring of medical devices and their environment, addressing a blind spot in security monitoring and reducing cybersecurity risk.
- And the cyber threat monitoring system (CTMS), that displays the information in an organized way and provides user-friendly interfaces to Security Operations Centre (SOC) analysts so that they can analyse and visualise threats and impacted assets.

The integrated cyber-physical security solutions rely on:

- The data exchange layer (DXL) implements publish-subscribe mechanisms in order to trigger notifications to the other components when new physical and cyber incident (coming from the BTMS and the CTMS) or new impacts (coming from the IPDSM) are sent.
- The central database (CDB) constitutes the pillar stone in order to build added-value indicators. Cross connecting data expands the capacity to create either more consistent results or innovative results.
- The impact propagation and decision support model (IPDSM), aiming a) to combine physical and cyber incidents that occur on assets, b) infer cascading effects as impacts that could potentially affect the same or related assets, and c) alert other modules about the potential impacts and severity.
- The threat response and alert system (TRAS), is in charge of sending alerts and notifications upon impact reception from the IPDSM, aiming to enable a fast response time in anticipation since the impact propagation model is using prediction.

- The hospital availability management system (HAMS) is in charge of managing hospital status, asset and resource availability, and visualize the different messages received from the other modules.
- And the e-health security risk management model, is developed to support the risk assessment process by quantifying security risks.

The SAFECARE solutions may be beneficial for the following cyber-physical use cases:

- Prevent Cyber-physical attack targeting power supply of the hospital.
- Prevent Cyber-physical attack to steal patient data in the hospital.
- Prevent Cyber-physical attack targeting the population, IT systems and medical devices in the hospital, and patient data base.
- Prevent Cyber-physical attack targeting the air-cooling system of the hospital.
- Prevent shooting, explosive or sabotage in critical places (visible or invisible).
- Theft at hospital equipment, access to hospital network and IT systems.
- IOT medical wearable devices (outside / inside).
- Distributed management over distributed buildings, considering external stakeholders (e.g., pharmacy, outpatients).
- Physical attack against hospital staff using a gun.
- Cyber-physical attack to block national crisis management.

Advantages of SAFECARE solutions include the following:

- Only one solution to detect and prevent all kind of threats, updates are available against new threats.
- Infrastructure is protected against all hazards.
- The solution is reliable and well-conceived as it is made by European Experts.
- To have a turnkey solution tailor made to healthcare infrastructures.
- The tool does not require any supplementary equipment purchases. It can be integrated into the infrastructure without supplementary integration costs.
- Adaptability and compatibility to all the infrastructure.
- The solution is able to detect physical and cyber-attacks and risks not only nationally but also at the EU level
- Detection and protection from a large panel of threats and attacks. The solution is built resilient.
- No additional controls are required
- Synchronized and accurate information, permanent and real-time alerts, pooled forces against threats.
- Enhanced communication, cooperation and decision-making, based on real-time, precise and accurate information following standard operating procedures.

- Automatic switch to a secondary server in case of a fail-down, continuity of services proved.
- Thin detection. Detection engines are modular (downgradable/upgradable) according to needs.
- Customization and automating of reports (intern and extern). Give the information to the teams. Capacity to prepare and overwhelm a risk crisis.
- Data collected secured from rob, infiltration, listening, redirections. High data availability, confidentiality, integrity.
- Risk mapping tool working with analysis engines.
- The solution is modular and customizable. The yearly expense can be reviewed or resized every year.
- Biomedical equipment (thus high value assets and critical equipment) are protected.
- Health and critical data are protected (as well as reputation).
- Healthcare vital supply, medicines, sensitive stocks, dangerous supplies are better protected.
- New types of threats are detected, it faces new attacks due to IPM Module, the cooperating sensors of which, are combined with smart and analytics engines, being able to stop the attacks.

Securing The European Gas Network (SecureGas) - GA 833017

SecureGas focuses on the 140.000Km of the European Gas network covering the entire value chain from Production to Distribution to the users, providing methodologies, tools and guidelines to secure existing and incoming installations and make them resilient to cyber-physical threats.

The technologies used by SecureGas to meet the needs of end users, address and solve the proposed business cases scenarios, adopting the most innovative technological solutions, without forgetting cost control and easy and scalable deployment, are the following:

Technologies for situational Awareness and Decision Support for Cyber-Physical Threats

Safety and Security platform for Gas CI, is a support framework to manage processes for critical infrastructures based on an OODA (Observe, Orient, Decide, and Act) methodology, supporting a wide-range of proactive or reactive prescriptive security activities to achieve strategic or tactical outcomes in an integrated security vision.

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) Correlator Engine based on Machine Learning and Pattern Matching identifies relationships among heterogeneous events, even apparently unrelated, generated by various subsystems, in order to generate new alarms (smart alarms) or identify possible false-positive
- (b) Intrusion prevention/detection in ICS/SCADA systems through behavioural analysis at different levels and threats recognition in the OT network
- (c) Decision Support functions: modelling and simulation of Infrastructures and Services aimed at identifying operating scenarios and possible propagation of anomalies on the

basis of data coming from the field. Prescription of the optimal course of action to be taken.

(d) DSS leverages on an Human Machine Interface that exposes a high level of Situation Awareness through displaying a CROP (Common Relevant Operational Picture) with all relevant information to understand what is happening within scenario. GIS functions allow an integrated management of cartography to provide the user a geo-referenced integrated view of all the information (e.g. UAV 3D surveillance data; fast predictive geo-referenced gas flow simulations pre, during and post events)

Autonomous docking station and UAV based asset management, covers the need to significantly reduce the effort and costs of UAV surveillance by resorting to electrical fast-recharging ultra-lightweight UAVs.

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) To have a control and management system of distributed inoffensive UAVs fleets using also IoT technology, with a low environmental impact (docking station of reduced size and power consumption) and very high level of operational safety (operational risks close to zero);
- (b) complete autonomous unattended and safe operations for selected areas steered within S&S;
- (c) low-cost transfer of high-quality imagery, multiple sensor data and flight information to S&S allowing assessment and analysis.

Onshore Landslide Susceptibility and Alert/Monitoring System, allows giving alert in case of heavy rainfall that could lead to landslides/debris flow.

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) Providing PaaS solution for landslide stability evaluation along pipeline routes including spatial extension assessment;
- (b) providing near-real-time assessments in the case of pipeline failures using S&S environment data;
- (c) improving the quality/quantity of inputs available for planning and decision making

Technologies for information processing and management

Cyber-physical correlator, to mine the increasing monitoring and surveillance data as well as from observing ICT and SCADA/ICS systems, for detecting anomalies projected to gas grids.

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) Real-time anomaly detection in health monitoring data of gas grids;
- (b) anomaly detection in gas grid SCADA, IT and IoT Systems data flows;
- (c) ML approach for intrusion patterns recognition (to be combined with the Safety and Security platform features and to the intrusion detection tool, and video surveillance capability);
- (d) implementation of proposed ICT mitigation measures based on root cause analysis.

Blockchain for data transmission and integrity verification

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) Use of KSI® blockchain technology as a means for building integrity verification mechanisms to protect the input provided by different SecureGAS modules and distributing these inputs between all trusted participants in the system.
- (b) The input can be flexible from securing the system logs and cyber incidents registry to the integrity verification of monitoring processes. Moreover, through the KSI® blockchain technology the capability to deal with Quantum computers will be added to the S&S platform.
- (c) The cryptography behind the KSI signatures ensures that they never expire and remain quantum-immune i.e. secure even after the realization of quantum computation. This is crucial to strengthen capabilities of CI against cyber and cyber physical threats.

Cyber Security for IT and OT networks weakness, which is a SCADA monitoring solution, providing asset mapping & real time SCADA protocols monitoring

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) SCADA network visibility > The end user receives clear visibility of its SCADA network, including all connected devices /assets and their communication protocols.
- (b) Cyber security > Unsecured devices utilising SCADA protocols receive an additional layer of security where the solution monitors the devices communication and alerts when suspicious behaviour / event is detected.
- (c) System and user's interfaces > Possibility to rely on the system interface to have more details on the anomalies detected

ARTEMIS platform, will be expanded to deliver physical security for nodes of the gas network. Heterogeneous inputs will be collected. Advanced algorithms will be developed, e.g., for correlation, reasoning, and for triggering mitigation actions.

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) Digital transformation of utilities.
- (b) Important use cases, coming from the vertical needs, addressed through innovative technologies.
- (c) Enhanced physical security of gas networks, nodes and sites.

Technologies for detection, identification and early warning

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) for monitoring of leakages and third-party intrusion in Oil and Gas pipelines

The main innovative elements are:

- (a) The key benefit of the proposed system is the detection, classification and geo-localization of third-party damages, fluids leaks and ground motion along hundreds of kilometres, in quasi-real time and with an unprecedented level of spatial resolution (below 10 m).

(b) The system can exploit already existing optical fibre infrastructure, typically installed adjacent to the pipeline for communication purposes, allowing users to monitor long linear assets in quasi-real time.

Cognitive framework and combined analytics for biometrics and video analytics, is based on video biometrics cameras to detect suspicious event and potential threats dangerous for the gas network integrity. The component is also characterized by an analytics part based on video recorded. The tool in fact is able to combine data coming from people's presence to check intrusion in different sites/facilities, comparing in this way different scenarios.

The main innovative elements are:

(a) Improved quality of alarms from automated video analytics: person, vehicle detection and tracking under low-light conditions using improved white list detection and deep learning networks; path prediction with area control based on improved track concatenation; and detection of persons, who intentionally hide their face at critical spots, as an anomaly.

(b) The main advantages coming from the use of video analytics are presence analytics and patterns of movement detection. Video analytics allows monitoring and checking any presence and intrusion periodically and repetitively.

Sensors for detection, identification and early warnings. These devices include all the pertinent sensors, connect them and use different communication protocols to send their data to the central servers.

The main innovative elements are:

(a) Multi-purpose devices, for monitoring multiple heterogeneous parameters

(b) Real-time monitoring in customizable frequency

(c) Different communication protocols depending on availability

(d) Embedded intelligence for early warning

Technologies for Joint Cyber-Physical Security Risk Management and Resilience Modelling

Joint Cyber-Physical Risk and Resilience Management, aims at providing support to the operators before, during and after an incident occurrence.

The main innovative elements are:

(a) A tool for systematic and consistent risk analysis and assessment of security breach scenarios, addressing all assets and systems that are established within the boundaries of the CI under study.

(b) Provide support to the operators before, during and after an incident occurrence, aiming at adding values to the main risk and resilience phases.

(c) Supports real time risk and resilience assessment capabilities, enabling the dynamic risk level estimation of the security incidents detected by the SecureGas system.

(d) Provides the operator real time recommendations on the actions that need to be performed for the absorption of an event, the efficient response to it and the fast recovery in case of disruption.

(e) Risk and resilience assessment regarding security threats and emerging risks for new Gas CI projects (design phase) shall support the implementation of a comprehensive all-hazards approach considering security, safety, technical and environmental aspects

Gas Network Advanced Modelling and Fast-Dynamics Simulation, that will enable the user to predict gas supply situations under various operational conditions. The software will also determine the vulnerability and importance ranking of network elements from the security of supply point of view based on an automated statistical evaluation of a large number of disruption scenarios.

The main innovative elements are:

(a) This component provides a statistical risk assessment which is based on the physical simulations of pipeline gas flows under disruption conditions.

(b) This allows for an informed decision making in regards to targeted reinforcement of weak points in the gas infrastructure.

(c) Support to a risk assessment study for an existing compressor station by identifying criticality/ranking of outgoing pipelines.

(d) Decision support for placing/connecting remote control for existing valves.

Risk-Aware Information to the population, will allow the coordination of information exchanged within the organization, as well as between the organization and the authorities. It will facilitate the public information and notification process.

The main innovative elements are:

(a) A novel model is proposed and will be developed in SecureGas, for the exchange of information about incidents between services and their control rooms.

(b) This will guarantee that information about the Location, Type of incident, Hazards present or suspected, Access, Casualties and Emergency services are shared in a consistent and transparent way, accurately and reliably.

The business cases of SecureGas cover the entire value chain focusing on:

- Risk-based approaches to security asset management across the life-cycle of gas transmission and distribution networks in compliance with the “Common Risk Assessment Approach” as required by EU Regulation 2017/1938;
- Impacts and cascading effects of cyber-physical attacks on vital nodes of interdependent and interconnected Gas transmission grids in line with the request of EU Regulation 2017/1938 of “running .. scenarios of disruption of gas supply (e.g. transmission infrastructure, storages) ...Assessing their likely consequences”;
- Integrity and security through the operationalization of resilience guidelines of strategic installations across the EU Gas network in line with the need to “develop and agree on preventive and emergency measures” as requested by EU Regulation 2017/1938.

Project NOWATER

(Hospital preparedness planning)

Emergency management planning of water server supply and disposal of health care facilities – organizational and technical solution strategies to increase resilience

Analyses the water supply and disposal as part of the critical elements of a hospital

Key Elements:

- **Risk Management:** Development of methods for risk analysis in case of failure of water supply and wastewater disposal in healthcare facilities, especially hospitals.
- **Emergency Preparedness Planning:** Creation of organizational and technical solution strategies to maintain water supply during crises.
- **Practical Solutions:** Development of a prototype for emergency water supply and creation of a practical guide for effective emergency preparedness and crisis management.
- **Goals**
- **Increasing Resilience:** Ensuring continuous water supply and wastewater disposal in medical facilities to maintain their functionality during crises.
- **Protecting Public Health:** Minimizing the impact of water outages on medical care and hygiene standards.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Promoting collaboration between the healthcare sector, disaster management, municipal administrations, and technical experts to develop comprehensive solutions.

Connection to the objectives of EU-CIP

NOWATER is a project that aims to impact German hospital emergency preparedness planning by focusing on water supply and disposal, highlighting their importance in this field. This can be seen as a trend implementation thereby connecting to Chapter 3.2 of the white paper.

Publications to the project

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Project Impress

(Decision Support; Healthcare)

IMproving Preparedness and Response of HHealth Services in major criseS

Key elements

- core taxonomy for the health services involved in emergency management, as well as a semantic reference model (ontology) for the specific domain
- a HEMS approach which is most suited for European countries deployment
- a new operating framework based upon a distributed, modular, scalable system

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

- an integrated and interoperable multi-agency coordination and collaboration
- training component and associated training material as well as lessons learned collection tool
- Goals
- Rebalance the disproportion between response needs and capacity
- Remediate the information deficits and decision-making problems with respect to the nature, scope and causes of crisis events that threaten the Health Status of a Com-munity
- Health services response and preparedness improvement
- Enhancement of Intra- and Inter-Organizational interoperability in EMS

Connection to the objectives of EU-CIP

As one of the sectors defined as CI, the health sector needs to stay in operation during major crisis especially. In order to achieve this the balance between the needs and the capacity has to be restored and the operability improved. That is what this project is aiming for.

Publications to the project

Ipektsidisi, Babis: IMPROVING PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE OF HEALTH SERVICES IN MAJOR CRISES. Final Report. Online available <https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/results/608/608078/final1-impress-final-report-publishablessummary-en-v1-0.pdf>, last visit 22.07.2024.

Liapis, Aggelos; Kostaridis, Antonis; Ramfos, Antonis; Hall, Ian; DeGaetano, Andrea; Koutras, Nickolaos et al. (2015): A Position Paper on Improving Preparedness and Response of Health Services in Major Crises.

Project S-HELP

(Decision Support; Healthcare)

Securing Health Emergency Learning and Planning

Key elements

- Phase 1: Research and Analysis
- Phase 2: Design and Development
- Phase 3: Training and Implementation
- Phase 4: Evaluation and Validation
- Goals
- develop and deliver a holistic framed approach to healthcare preparedness, response and recovery
- advance the knowledge base required for the development of a range of Decision Support (DS) tools and a Decision Support System (DSS) for the management of all Emergency Medicine activities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Connection to the objectives of EU-CIP

The health sector is an important part of the functioning of modern society. It's functionality is of high importance. This project contributes to a more resilient health sector.

Publications to the projects

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Collins, Matthew; Neville, Karen; Hynes, William; Madden, Martina (2016): Communication in a disaster - the development of a crisis communication tool within the S-HELP project. In: Journal of Decision Systems 25 (sup1), S. 160–170. DOI: 10.1080/12460125.2016.1187392.

Conrado, Silvia Planella; Neville, Karen; Woodworth, Simon; O'Riordan, Sheila (2016): Man-aging social media uncertainty to support the decision-making process during Emergencies. In: Journal of Decision Systems 25 (sup1), S. 171–181. DOI: 10.1080/12460125.2016.1187396.

McCarthy, Nora; Neville, Karen; Pope, Andrew; Gallagher, Anthony; Nussbaumer, Alexan-der; Steiner, Christina M. (2016): The creation of a training model to support decision-making of emergency management practitioners: a design research study. In: Journal of Decision Systems 25 (sup1), S. 558–565. DOI: 10.1080/12460125.2016.1187409.

Neville, Karen; O'Riordan, Sheila; Pope, Andrew; Rauner, Marion; Maria Rochford; Madden, Martina et al. (2016): Towards the development of a decision support system for multi-agency decision-making during cross-border emergencies. In: Journal of Decision Systems 25 (sup1), S. 381–396. DOI: 10.1080/12460125.2016.1187393.

Project SNOWBALL

(decision support; Lower the impact of aggravating factors in crisis situations thanks to adaptative foresight and decision-support tools

Key elements

- deep analysis of cascading effects and development of methods to anticipate them
- Decision Support System that is able to display current crisis monitoring and results of simulated decisions integrating cascading effects
- creation of a general platform containing different tools to simulate or follow a crisis and allow better preparedness

Goals

- increase the preparedness of the European Union in respect to hazards that could amplify a large crisis
- Apprehend and better predict and simulate the cascading effects that occur in a crisis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

- Integrate population response and behaviour to the simulation tools
- Provide decision support to public authorities and decision makers in the light of cascading effects simulations
- Test the efficiency of the tool in the frame of various demonstrations

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

The failure of a CI can cause a major crisis set aside if several CI's fail to stay in operation. The project identifies and predicts cascading effects and creates tools to deal with them for public authorities and decision makers.

Publications to the project

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Hahm, Stefanie; Kietzmann, Diana; Lemanski, Sandra; Knuth, Daniela; Schmidt, Silke (2019): Factors of perceived threat regarding severe storm events: Results of a vignette study in four European countries. In: *Safety Science* 116, S. 26–32. DOI: 10.1016/j.ssci.2019.02.026.

Jean-Pierre Bidau, M.: Snowball. Project final report. Online available <https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/results/606/606742/final1-snowball-finalreport-v5.pdf>, last visit 26.07.2024.

Zuccaro, Giulio; Gregorio, Daniela de; Leone, Mattia F. (2018): Theoretical model for cascading effects analyses. In: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 30, S. 199–215. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdrr.2018.04.019.

Project STOP-IT

(risk management concepts; water Infrastructure)

Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats

Key elements

- co-develops an all-hazards risk management framework for the physical and cyber protection of critical water infrastructures
- generate modular solutions that will be embedded into an integrated, scalable, adaptable and modular software platform

Goals

- identify current and future risks
- to develop a comprehensive risk management concept for the physical and cyber security of critical water infrastructures

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

Water infrastructures are vital for the functioning of human societies. The water sector is identified as a critical infrastructure (CI); hence, the project aims to protect these facilities by developing a risk management concept.

Publications to the project

EasyChair (Hg.) (2018): HIC 2018. 13th International Conference on Hydroinformatics. With support from Goffredo La Loggia, Gabriele Freni, Valeria Puleo und Mauro de Marchis. EPiC Series in Engineering. 3. Aufl.: EasyChair.

Gonzalez-Granadillo, Gustavo; Diaz, Rodrigo; Caubet, Juan; Garcia-Milà, Ignasi (2021): CLAP: A Cross-Layer Analytic Platform for the Correlation of Cyber and Physical Security Events Affecting Water Critical Infrastructures. In: Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy 1 (2), S. 365–386. DOI: 10.3390/jcp1020020.

González-Granadillo, Gustavo; González-Zarzosa, Susana; Diaz, Rodrigo (2021): Security Information and Event Management (SIEM): Analysis, Trends, and Usage in Critical Infra-structures. In: Sensors 21 (14). DOI: 10.3390/s21144759.

Granadillo, Gustavo; Diaz, Rodrigo; Karali, Theodora; Caubet, Juan; Garcia-Milà, Ignasi (2021): 8. Cyber-Physical Solutions for Real-time Detection, Analysis and Visualization at Operational Level in Water CIs. In:

Hassanzadeh Amin; Rasekh Amin; Galelli Stefano; Aghashahi Mohsen; Taormina Riccardo; Ostfeld Avi; Banks M. Katherine (2020): A Review of Cybersecurity Incidents in the Water Sector. In: Journal of Environmental Engineering 146 (5), S. 3120003. DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0001686.

Moraitis Georgios; Nikolopoulos Dionysios; Bouziotas Dimitrios; Lykou Archontia; Karavokiros George; Makropoulos Christos (2020): Quantifying Failure for Critical Water Infrastructures under Cyber-Physical Threats. In: Journal of Environmental Engineering 146 (9), S. 4020108. DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0001765.

N. Bakalos; A. Voulodimos; N. Doulamis; A. Doulamis; A. Ostfeld; E. Salomons et al. (2019): Protecting Water Infrastructure From Cyber and Physical Threats: Using Multimodal Data Fusion and Adaptive Deep Learning to Monitor Critical Systems. In: IEEE Signal Processing Magazine 36 (2), S. 36–48. DOI: 10.1109/MSP.2018.2885359.

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Nikolopoulos, Dionysios; Moraitis, Georgios; Makropoulos, Christos (2021): 7. Strategic and Tactical Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Water Infrastructures. In:

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Ugarelli, Rita (2021): 6. Cybersecurity Importance in the Water Sector and the Contribution of the STOP-IT Project. In:

Ugarelli, Rita; Koti, Juliane; Bonet, Enric; Makropoulos, Christos; Caubet, Juan; Camarinopoulos, Stephanos et al. (2018): STOP-IT - Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of Water Infrastructure

Against Cyber-Physical Threats. In: EasyChair (Hg.): HIC 2018. 13th International Conference on Hydroinformatics. With support from Goffredo La Loggia, Gabriele Freni, Valeria Puleo und Mauro de Marchis. 3. Aufl.: EasyChair, S. 2112–2119. Online available <https://easychair.org/publications/paper/zJL7>, last visit 26.07.2024.

Project DRIVER+

(Crisis management)

DRiving InnoVation in crisis management for European Resilience

Key elements

- five Subprojects (SPs)
- Project Management is devoted to consortium level project management, and it is also in charge of the alignment of DRIVER+ with external initiatives on Crisis Management for the benefit of DRIVER+ and its stakeholders. In DRIVER+, all activities related to Societal Impact Assessment
- Test-bed will deliver a guidance methodology and guidance tool supporting the design, conduct and analysis of Trials and will develop a reference implementation of the Test-bed. It will also create the scenario simulation capability to support execution of the Trials.
- Solutions will deliver the Portfolio of Solutions which is a database driven web site that documents all the available DRIVER+ solutions, as well as solutions from external organisations. Adapting solutions to fit the needs addressed in Trials.
- Trials will organize four series of Trials as well as the Final Demo (FD).
- Impact, Engagement and Sustainability, is in charge of communication and dissemination, and also addresses issues related to improving sustainability, market aspects of solutions, and standardisation.

Goals

- improving the way capability development and innovation management is tackled
- Develop a pan-European Test-bed for Crisis Management capability development
- Develop a well-balanced comprehensive Portfolio of Crisis Management Solutions
- Facilitate a shared understanding of Crisis Management across Europe

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

- A better crisis management helps to keep CI's in operation in case of a disaster or attack.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Publications to the project

Borges, Marcos; Canós-Cerdá, José; Penadés, M^a; Labaka, Leire; Bañuls, Víctor; Hernantes, Josune (2023): Toward a Taxonomy for Classifying Crisis Information Management Systems. In.; S. 409–433.

Detzer, Sandra; Gurczik, Gaby; Widera, Adam; Nitschke, Annika (2016): Assessment of Logistic and Traffic Management Tool-Suites for Crisis Management.

Dubost, Laurent; Boisson, Jean-Michel; Quere, Bruno; Giroud, Frederique; Clemenceau, Alice (2017): Trialing a common operational picture in a simulated environment a DRIVER project trial.

Flötteröd, Yun-Pang; Erdmann, Jakob (2016): Experiment Study on the Evacuation of Bomb Alert with SUMO.

Granåsen, Dennis; Eriksson, Pär (2015): Inter-organisational lessons learned: Perspectives and challenges.

Havlik, Denis; Lampert, Jasmin; Widera, Adam (2016): Interaction with Citizens Experiments: From Context-aware Alerting to Crowdtasking.

Horndahl, Andreas; Gisslén, Linus (2015): Dynamic and Context Aware Reporting of Observations from the Field for Situation Assessment in Crisis Situation: An Integrated System for Information-Gathering and Sense-Making.

K. Lechner; M. Gähler (2017): Earth observation based crisis information — Emergency mapping services and recent operational developments. In: 2017 4th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Disaster Management (ICT-DM). 2017 4th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Disaster Management (ICT-DM), S. 1–7.

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Rocha, Roberto; Widera, Adam; van den Berg, Roelof; Albuquerque, Joao de; Hellingrath, Bernd (2016): Improving the Involvement of Digital Volunteers in Disaster Management.

Schwoch, Gunnar; Geister, Dagi; Rudolph, Michael; Zillies, Julia (2016): Enhancing Un-manned Flight Operations in Crisis Management with Live Aerial Images.

Tagarev, Todor; Ratchev, Valeri (2018): Evolving Models of Using Armed Forces in Domestic Disaster Response and Relief. In: Information & Security: An International Journal 40, S. 167–180. DOI: 10.11610/isij.4012.

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Widera, Adam; Hellingrath, Bernd (2016): Making Performance Measurement Work in Humanitarian Logistics - The Case of an IT-supported Balanced Scorecard. In., S. 339–352.

Widera, Adam; Middelhoff, Michael; Hellingrath, Bernd; Auferbauer, Daniel; Lampert, Jasmin; Havlik, Denis (2016): Crowdsourcing and Crowdtasking in Crisis Management: Lessons Learned From a Field Experiment Simulating a Flooding in City of the Hague.

Project ATLANTIS

(Systemic resilience; vulnerability assessment; cooperation between CI operators and government stakeholders)

Key elements

- 3 large-scale cross-border and cross-sector pilots
- Cross-Border/Cross Domain Large Scale Pilot in Transport, Energy and Tele-coms
- Cross Domain Large Scale Pilot in Health, Logistics/Supply Chain and Border control
- Cross-Country Large-Scale Pilot in FinTech/Financial

Goals

- Improve knowledge on large-scale, vulnerability assessment and long-term systemic risks
- Improve the systemic resilience of European Critical Infrastructure (ECI), through novel, adaptive, flexible, and customizable security measures (“by design”) and tools (“by innovation”)
- Effective cooperation among CI operators and government security stakeholders, while preserving CI autonomy and sovereignty
- Deliver an open technological framework that will provide the ECIs with AI -based solutions for increased AWARENESS, CAPABILITY and COOPERATION in managing systemic threats

Connection to the objectives of EU-CIP

The interconnectedness of the modern world with its infrastructure requires a broad approach to secure these facilities. The project delivers new security measures and tools to combat cyber-physical threats against CIs.

Publications to the project

Dinu, Vladut; Plesa, Alexandru; Jarca, Andrei; Vintila, Cristian Raul; Nechifor, Cosmin-Septimiu; Ilie, Iulia: Enhancing Risk Reduction and Incident Mitigation Through Automated Explainable

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

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Voukaidis, Artemis: The CCI-SAAM Framework. Online available <https://www.atlantis-horizon.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/ATLANTIS-The-CCI-SAAM-Framework.pdf>, last visit 26.07.2024.

Project LINKS

(Administration; connecting stakeholders)

Strengthening links between technologies and society for European disaster resilience

Key elements

- comprehensive study on disaster governance in Europe
- producing sustainable advanced learning on the use of social media and crowdsourcing in disasters
- integrative research approach

Goals

- strengthen links between technologies and society for improved European disaster resilience
- LINKS Framework which consists of scientific methods, practical tools, and guidelines addressing researchers, practitioners, and policy makers to understand, measure and govern social media and crowdsourcing for disasters
- create the LINKS Community, which brings together a wide variety of stakeholders, both online (LINKS Community Center) and in person (LINKS Community Work-shops)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

By studying disaster governance in Europe, the project aims to link public authorities and their procedures more closely together, thereby improving the resiliency of European societies.

Publications to the project

Bonati, Sara; Nardini, Olga; Boersma, Kees; Clark, Nathan (2023): Unravelling dynamics of vulnerability and social media use on displaced minors in the aftermath of Italian earthquakes. In: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 89, S. 103632. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdr.2023.103632.

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Project MEDiate

(Decision support; risk management)

Multi-hazard and risk informed system for Enhanced local and regional Disaster risk management

Key elements

- analysis of relevant data
- co-development with testbed decision-makers of a decision-support system to enable more reliable resilience assessments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Goals

- develop a decision-support system for disaster risk management by considering multiple interacting natural hazards and cascading impacts using a novel resilient-informed and service-oriented approach
- decision support framework in the form of a service-orientated web tool
- disaster risk management framework

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

The project's developments will allow users to evaluate the potential impact of different risk management strategies to reduce vulnerability and enhance community resilience. This helps policymakers produce evidence-based policies.

Publications to the project

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Lee, Ryan; White, Christopher J.; Adnan, Mohammed Sarfaraz Gani; Douglas, John; Mahecha, Miguel D.; O'Loughlin, Fiachra E. et al. (2024): Reclassifying historical disasters: From single to multi-hazards. In: Science of The Total Environment 912, S. 169120. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169120.

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Project RESILOC

(resilience of communities)

Resilient Europe and Societies by Innovating Local Communities

Key elements

- holistic framework of studies, methods and software instruments will be developed

STUDY

- Collection and analysis of literature and stories from the many approaches to resilience adopted across Europe and all over the World
- Definition of a classification for the functions that are critical to resilience of communities, extending the realm currently adopted for measuring resilience in cities
- Definition of terms, indexes and correlations between indexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

METHODS AND STRATEGIES

- Assessment of the resilience indexes of a community, together with simulations on the “what-if” certain measures are taken
- Identification of new and better approaches to (e.g.) communicate with citizens, reduce the vulnerability of infrastructures, launch awareness campaigns on risks and adopt technological solutions to improve the understanding and the monitoring of critical infrastructures
- Local Resilience Teams

SOFTWARE INSTRUMENTS

- RESILOC inventory, a comprehensive, live, structure for collecting, classifying and using information on cities and local communities, implemented as a Software as a Service
- RESILOC Cloud-based platform for assessing and calculating the resilience indicators of any participating city or community

Goals

- Increase the understanding of resilience in societies and local communities
- Innovate on the strategies for improving resilience
- Innovate on tools and solutions for improving on resilience in communities
- Communicate, demonstrate and assess the validity of approaches, solutions and tools in field trials
- Have an impact and define concrete steps towards a more resilient society

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

On a local level, the project helps to increase the resiliency of European communities and its results contribute to a higher level of knowledge for the safety of the European society.

Publications to the project

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Project ENGAGE

(resilience of communities)

Key elements

- analyse past natural emergencies, terrorist attacks, and man-made disasters
- understand how citizens supported formal intervention practices during emergencies under specific contextual conditions
- propose emergency response strategies to bring the population closer to rescuers and authorities

Goals

- tries to bridge the different ways of intervention to make communities more skilled in responding to disasters jointly
- make communities more resilient

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

The ENGAGE project strengthens local communities in the field of crisis management. This enhancement of resilience through preparedness in the operational aspects of crisis management contributes to the overall resilience of critical infrastructure

Publications to the project

Bodas, Moran; Peleg, Kobi; Stolerio, Nathan; Adini, Bruria (2022): Risk Perception of Natural and Human-Made Disasters—Cross Sectional Study in Eight Countries in Europe and Be-yond. In: *Frontiers in Public Health* 10. DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.825985.

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Elkady, Sahar; Hernantes, Josune; Gómez, Eulalia; Labaka, Leire (2024): Revealing resilience features: Analyzing informal solutions adopted in emergency situations. In: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 101, S. 104267. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.104267.

Elkady, Sahar; Hernantes, Josune; Labaka, Leire (2023): Towards a resilient community: A decision support framework for prioritizing stakeholders' interaction areas. In: *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 237, S. 109358. DOI: 10.1016/j.res.2023.109358.

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Elkady, Sahar; Hernantes, Josune; Muñoz, Mar; Labaka, Leire (2022): What do emergency services and authorities need from society to better handle disasters? In: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 72, S. 102864. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdrr.2022.102864.

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Project BuildERS

(resilience of communities)

Building European Communities' Resilience and Social Capital

Key elements

- Providing an understanding of and how the most vulnerable people exposed to risks and threats understand risks, prepare for and behave individually and collectively in crisis
- Creating knowledge to empower and activate first-responders, policy makers, administrators, public and private service providers and citizens
- Analysing and providing insights on how new technologies and media could improve disaster resilience of societies
- Providing policy recommendations to the relevant stakeholders to maximize the usability and reliability of social media in disasters and recovery processes

Goals

- increase understanding of societal resilience
- strengthen social capital, risk awareness and preparedness of the vulnerable segments of societies and communities

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

One of the main objectives of the project is to provide data-driven policy recommendations, which is also an objective of the EU-CIP project. Moreover, it focuses on vulnerable segments of societies, which can be CIs.

Publications to the project

Berawi, Mohammed Ali; Leviäkangas, Pekka; Siahaan, Sutan Akbar Onggar; Hafidza, Alya; Sari, Mustika; Miraj, Perdana et al. (2021): Increasing disaster victim survival rate: SaveMy-Life Mobile Application development. In: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 60, S. 102290. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102290.

Gunawan, Mohammed Ali Berawi, Pekka Leviäkangas, Fadhi Muhammad, Mustika Sari, Yandi Andri Yatmo, Muhammad Suryanegara (2019): Optimizing Search and Rescue Personnel Allocation in

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Disaster Emergency Response using Fuzzy Logic. In: *International Journal of Technology* 10 (7), S. 291–319. DOI: 10.14716/ijtech.v10i7.3709.

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Project KIRMin

(Resilience concept for CI)

German Title: “Kritische Infrastrukturen-Resilienz als Mindestversorgungskonzept“ translates to: „Resilience of critical infrastructures as concept of minimum supply“

- Analysis of interdependencies in critical infrastructure in Germany
- Therefore, analysis of the impact of a power outage on water supply and other CI
- Focus on the necessary minimum supply for the population in case of a (partial) failure of basic supply
- Creation of a concept for minimum supply of CI during a power outage
- Development of adequate risk management based on the identified dependencies
- Evaluation of preventive measures for risk avoidance and minimization
- Integration of the minimum supply concept into the risk and crisis management pro-cess

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

KIRMin highlights interdependencies of the elements of critical infrastructure, and thereby it helps to strengthen the resilience of CI.

Publications to the Project

Dierich, Axel; Tzavella, Katerina; Setiadi, Neysa; Fekete, Alexander; Neisser, Florian (2019): Enhanced Crisis-Preparation of Critical Infrastructures through a Participatory Qualitative-Quantitative Interdependency Analysis Approach. Online available https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333190590_Enhanced_Crisis-Preparation_of_Critical_Infrastructures_through_a_Participatory_Qualitative-Quantitative_Interdependency_Analysis_Approach.

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Website: <https://kirmin.web.th-koeln.de/> (german)

Alexander Fekete, Alexander Lechleuthner, Ompe Aime Mudimu

Project PRAETORIAN

(cyber; increasing resilience)

Protection of Critical Infrastructures from advanced combined cyber and physical threats

Key elements

- multidimensional (economical, technological, policy, societal) installation-specific tool-set
- gather huge amounts of heterogeneous data from the different sectorial CIs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

- Physical Situation Awareness will analyse information received from different kind of physical sensors
- Cyber Situation Awareness will explore the network and CI's Information System to identify malicious patterns
- alarms raised by PSA and CSA will be processed by the Hybrid Situation Awareness (HSA) and will estimate the cascading effects in the own and related CIs

Goals

- increase the security and resilience of European CIs
- facilitating the coordinated protection of interrelated CI against combined physical and cyber threats

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

It provides a new toolset developed with CI stakeholders to protect their facilities.

Publications to the project

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M. A. Lozano; I. P. Llopis; A. C. Alarcón; M. E. Domingo (2023): A Machine Learning-Driven Threat Hunting Architecture for Protecting Critical Infrastructures. In: 2023 19th International Conference on the Design of Reliable Communication Networks (DRCN). 2023 19th International Conference on the Design of Reliable Communication Networks (DRCN), S. 1–5.

Schauer, Stefan; Latzenhofer, Martin; König, Sandra; Chlup, Sebastian; Schmittner, Christoph (2022): Application of a Generic Digital Twin for Risk and Resilience Assessment in Critical Infrastructures.

Stelkens-Kobsch, Tim H.; Boumann, Hilke; Piekert, Florian; Schaper, Meilin; Carstengerdes, Nils (2023): A Concept-Based Validation Approach to Validate Security Systems for Protection of Interconnected Critical Infrastructures. In: Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on

Availability, Reliability and Security. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery (ARES '23).

Project SMARTResilience

(Resilience; case study on CI)

Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures

Key elements

- identifying existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of SCIs
- identifying new “smart” resilience indicators
- developing a new advanced resilience assessment methodology
- developing the interactive “SCI Dashboard” tool
- applying the methodology/tools in 8 case studies

Goals

- benchmarking the best-practice solutions and identifying the early warnings
- improving resilience of SCIs against new threats and cascading and ripple effects

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

The project aims to improve modern smart systems of Critical Infrastructures (CIs) by extending their resiliency from daily dangers to more unusual events like natural disasters.

Publications to the project

IRGC Resource Guide on Resilience (2016).

Brauner, Florian; Claßen, Marie; Fiedrich, Frank (2018): Competence as Enabler of Urban Critical Infrastructure Resilience Assessment. In: Alexander Fekete und Frank Fiedrich (Hg.): Urban Disaster Resilience and Security: Addressing Risks in Societies. Cham: Springer International Publishing, S. 171–184.

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Project INFRARISK

(stress test methods CI, natural hazards)

“Novel Indicators for identifying critical INFRAstructure at RISK from natural hazards – INFRARISK”

Objectives

- Focus on identifying infrequent natural hazards with potential extreme impacts on critical infrastructure.
- Create a stress test framework for specific natural hazards affecting CI networks, especially linear systems like roads, highways, and railroads, with potential applications to other networks (for example telecommunication, energy).
- Develop a comprehensive hazard assessment method that considers:
 - Interdependencies of infrastructure networks
 - Correlated nature of natural hazards
 - Cascading hazards and effects
 - Spatial and temporal vulnerability
- Facilitate practical implementation by developing GIS-based and web-based stress test algorithms for complex infrastructure networks.
- Test the developed framework by simulating complex case studies.
- Develop exploitation strategies to disseminate knowledge beyond just results, including training courses for industry, academia, and media.

Connection to the objectives of our project EU-CIP

INFRARISK supports the EU-CIP project by developing methods to identify rare natural hazards and stress-test structures for ci, implemented via GIS/web algorithms and validated through complex simulations.

Publications to the Project

Clarke, Julie; Lam, Juan Carlos; Gehl, Pierre; Taalab, Khaled; Corbally, Robert (2016): Risk assessment for an Italian road network due to an extreme earthquake hazard scenario and the associated landslide cascading effects. Online available https://www.infrarisk-fp7.eu/sites/default/files/docs/CERI_Infrarisk_Paper_Camera_Ready.pdf, last visit 01.08.2024.

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9.2. Annex A.2: Transformations and Trends introduced

Critical Infrastructures (CIs) face numerous cyber-physical threats that can affect citizens' lives and habits, increase their feelings of insecurity, and influence the seamless services provision. During such incidents, but also in general for the security of CIs several internal and external stakeholders are involved, having different needs and requirements, trying to cooperate, respond and recover. Although CIs security management process is well analysed in each sector there is a need to set a common ground among different CIs, thus reducing administration/coordination overhead and

rendering the decision-making and crisis management process more efficient. Based on the findings of three EU-funded research projects (SATIE, SecureGas and SAFECARE), that aim to improve the physical and cyber security of CIs in a seamless and cost-effective way, the need for a global, cyber-physical security management and joint coordination approach, is identified³.

In more detail, the following recommendations are made that can enhance CIs' crisis management process, but also security as a whole: (a) CIs need to develop security plans and implement integrated physical and cyber security solutions (at a minimum common level depending on their needs) to protect their critical assets across their infrastructure; (b) CIs should integrate into their organisational structure a Holistic Security Operation Centre (HSOC) to detect, analyse, and manage cyber and physical attacks and to efficiently coordinate processes, people and technologies. Thus, a common operational picture will be achieved, and efficient information sharing will be facilitated, in order to alert operators and involved stakeholders to any potential threats or incidents and; (c) The establishment of a National Coordination Centre (NCC) for CIP is also of high value. The NCC will interact with the HSOC of each CI, but also with external stakeholders and other Coordination or Operational Centre (e.g. ERCC) on an international level. The main services and capabilities provided to the CI operators include risk and impact assessment, information gathering and sharing, and coordination of an incident and; (d) A common cyber-physical crisis management process should be established and followed within each CI and at Member States level.

On top of the above recommendations, a fundamental precondition for the enhancement of the security and protection of CIs is a common centre for information sharing, reporting of problems, and exchanging of good practices. To this end, the implementation of a National Coordination Centre (NCC) for CIP which interacts with a Holistic Security Operations Centre (HSOC) within each CI is crucial. The HSOCs will manage internally in each CI the cyber and physical security in a seamless and integrated way while acting as the single contact point between the CI and the NCC. The NCC will be the central node of the proposed approach, fully compliant with European standards, used for: i) assessing risk and map hazards and threats, assisting in this way the CI operator to assess a specific risk and gather information for setting the appropriate level of security, ii) incident reporting and information sharing with external stakeholders, such as Emergency Response Services (e.g. Police, Fire Service, Civil Protection, CERT, etc.), Public Organizations/Bodies (e.g. Ministries, Regulatory Authorities, NIS, etc.), iii) information sharing with inter-connected Infrastructures, providing the necessary information about an incident and impact propagation, in order to be prepared and avoid cascading effects, iv) exchange of information and further communication with other Coordination or Operational Centres, on one hand at national level e.g. National Civil Protection Coordination Centre, 112, etc., which in its turn would provide the necessary information to the public in a structured and organised way; and on the other hand at European or International level, e.g. the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) in Brussels, which will contact relevant Member States and organisations, if needed.

The integration of the security of CIs at the national (and at the EU level for those of European interest) is linked with the concept of interdependency and interconnection of the infrastructures. It is common practice that each infrastructure takes care of the needs to ensure their business continuity, but they are rather indifferent of the challenges the disruption of their services may cause. Their responsibility ends up with providing compensation for the related impact according to signed Service Level Agreements (SLA). However, such compensation doesn't address the impact on the

³ Mantzana, V., Georgiou, E., Gazi, A., Gkotsis, I., Chasiotis, I., Eftychidis, G. (2021). Towards a Global CIs' Cyber-Physical Security Management and Joint Coordination Approach. In: Abie, H., et al. Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection. CPS4CIP 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 12618. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69781-5_11

national economy and the societal disruption linked to the loss of services due to interdependencies with CIs that fail to address a security incident. This is what a State Security Organization must ensure through a proper monitoring structure.

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GFT Italia SRL ([GFT](#)), Italy
Inov instituto de engenharia de sistemas e computadores inovacao ([INO](#)), Portugal
Inlecom commercial pathways company limited by guarantee ([ICP](#)), Ireland
SINTEF AS ([SIN](#)), Norway
Steinbeis EU-VRI GMBH ([EU-VRI](#)), Germany
Stowarzyszenie Polska Platforma bezpieczeństwa wewnętrznego ([PPHS](#)), Poland
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Innov - Acts Limited ([INNOV](#)), Cyprus
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European Organisation for Security ([EOS](#)), Belgium
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven ([KUL](#)), Belgium
Fstechnology SPA ([FST](#)), Italy
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